

ARDC Persistent Identifier (PID) Portfolio Review

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April 23 2020 v.2

Prepared for Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)

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Executive Summary

This review was commissioned in 2019 by ARDC's Director of Data and Services. The remit was to evaluate ARDC's current persistent identifier (PID) portfolio, and to recommend future business planning and development activities for the component PIDs and services within it.

Research was conducted from September 2019 to February 2020. Landscape analyses were complemented by interviews with ARDC staff and partners, PID providers, and domain experts. While each PID chosen for review was evaluated individually, an agreed set of overarching principles was chosen to ensure consistency and clarity of purpose across the review (See page 13). While the individual review documents were under preparation, regular meetings with the ARDC team helped to shape the structure and context for this synthesis report.

The initial analysis confirmed that PIDs are a key dependency for many ARDC services, and PIDs are adopted and used throughout the research lifecycle. The FAIR data principles are a significant driver for ARDC's PIDs agenda (and widespread adoption of PIDs more generally).

ARDC is both a provider and consumer of PIDs, and has become established as a major player in the international PID community. ARDC's leadership in the PID sector has been hard-won over many years of engagement and partnership and is widely valued. This has strengthened ARDC's partnerships and strategic effectiveness globally, to the benefit of Australian research, and therefore it makes sense to build on this role.

PIDs support the discoverability of research data and associated entities by locating them in globally connected information systems. They help to enrich metadata and provide valuable contextual information, vital for the preservation and reusability of the data themselves. PIDs are designed to improve the availability and interoperability of information about the entities they identify, and so are extremely valuable for the aggregation and analysis of research data (and metadata). This value is particularly pronounced at scale: local reference numbers are frequently re-used or duplicated across contexts (as in the case of the six digit grant number used by many funding agencies) and the unique reference that PIDs provide is crucial for accuracy and integrity. Finally, PIDs enable us to assess and communicate the excellence of Australian research to domestic and global stakeholders by supporting stable citation for research data and associated entities. These citations help funders and employers to track and capture the downstream impact of research data.

The ARDC PID portfolio is well balanced, and close to comprehensive. The highest priority entities relevant to research data and to ARDC's strategic goals are, broadly speaking, included. Some work is needed to improve coverage of the various PID systems. There are risks which need to be mitigated (some technical, some social, some financial) but with clear management and active portfolio management over the coming years, none should prove insurmountable.

Given that PIDs, as noted, are pervasive in ARDC services, inaction is not an option for any of the PIDs included in this review. Any exit strategy would take careful planning and execution,

and the consequent gaps in provision would then need to be addressed. In light of this, the goal of this review has been to optimise the effectiveness of the PID portfolio as an enabler of Australian research excellence, integrity and impact whilst seeking routes to sustainability (such as cost recovery models for ARDC provided services, or technical resilience).

The key recommendations for each of the eight PIDs analysed in this review are summarised here. Chapter three provides more detailed 'scorecard' encapsulations of each of the reviews, and the full reports are appended to this document.

Key recommendations

ARDC's portfolio of PIDs has evolved in lockstep with its research data services. They successfully underpin the discoverability, interoperability and internationalisation of the Australian research data network. Overall, this review finds that ARDC needs to consolidate its PID offerings, and make some targeted investments with an eye to robustness and long-term sustainability, and in some cases potential independence from ARDC. PID by PID, the main recommendations are:

- 1) The *Research Activity Identifier* (RAiD) fills a critical gap in the research data landscape, and ARDC should invest resources and leverage the support of international partners to develop RAiD into a sustainable, global infrastructure in its own right. (See page 15)
- 2) *DataCite DOIs* are a means to ensure that Australian research is fed into global discovery services and linked to other outputs, such as articles and software. As costs rise, the sector will need to be educated on the benefits this brings, and helped to improve their usage of DataCite services. This could be facilitated by greater member interaction with DataCite's central systems, such as Fabrica for minting DOIs. (See page 16)
- 3) Organisations are vital to the FAIRness of research, but organisation identifiers are poorly and inconsistently implemented. ARDC should adopt the *Research Organization Registry* (ROR) identifier as its primary PID for organisations, and leverage its network to assure the sustainability of the initiative. (See page 17)
- 4) ARDC should begin to register DOIs for its investments, using the *Crossref Grant ID* service, and push for these to be integrated into services, such as Research Data Australia, and partner repositories. (See page 18)
- 5) *Instruments* represent a huge investment, and are fundamental to the nature and meaning of data. ARDC should continue to engage with national and international initiatives to provide PIDs and associated metadata for instruments. (See page 19)
- 6) ARDC should improve the robustness of the infrastructure for its *Handle* server, and collaborate internationally to ensure the persistence of the service. (See page 20)
- 7) *ORCID* is the de facto standard for researcher identification, and ARDC should support the Australian consortium in its benefits realisation work, and actively seek to improve interactions between ORCID and ARDC services to maximise the return on Australia's investment in ORCID adoption and integration. (See page 21)

- 8) The *Australian Government Linked Data Working Group* has developed a lightweight, flexible URI-based identifier system, which should be evaluated as a complement to ARDC's other PID approaches and as a means to strengthen links to the federal and state governments and facilitate access to government information resources. (See page 22)

1. Introduction

ARDC's mission is to bring competitive research advantage through data. It is a transformational, sector-wide initiative, working with research, government, and industry partners to build a coherent national and collaborative research data commons. This means that the data Australian researchers produce need to be easily and accurately findable. They need to be tied unambiguously to the researchers and organizations that produced them. Research data need to acknowledge support given by Australian government funding to that research, and expose connections to projects, infrastructure, instruments, facilities, and collaborators so that the context and means of its production can be understood.

All of these entities and the connections and relationships between them need to be a highly visible part of the global research information network if they are to showcase Australian excellence on the world stage. Over the last few decades, a global network of persistent identifier (PID) systems has emerged to track and describe all of these entities. ARDC services have incorporated these tools, helped them to evolve and generated new partnership and investment opportunities. In handling data at an industrial scale, PIDs are an essential engineering toolkit for managing a global mesh of hundreds of millions of information entities.

This document summarises the main findings of a review commissioned by the ARDC Data and Services team. The review set out to assess ARDC's current portfolio of PID integrations and to propose a roadmap for their future evolution. These PIDs are central to ARDC's strategic priorities: ensuring the quality of data services; providing coherence between research platforms and supporting infrastructure; promoting innovative approaches to the use, sharing and storage of data and tools; and generating high-value partnerships with institutions, both domestically and internationally.

ARDC has built up a suite of state-of-the-art tools to uniquely identify data, people, organisations, funding, projects, and more. These tools exist to serve Australian innovation and are themselves innovative. They deliver insight into the impact and adoption of cutting edge research, and enable researchers, funders and policy makers to assess the quality and integrity of the Australian research enterprise.

The review takes as its starting point the recognition that PIDs have emerged as a critical dependency and point of interaction between ARDC services and international information flows. The rationale for this analysis details the strategic and practical importance of PIDs to ARDC and Australian research. This summary outlines the key findings of the review in a simple

scorecard format. Each scorecard is based on a separate detailed analysis. Those analyses are present here as appendices to the summary report.

2. Review context and rationale

There are two primary reasons PIDs matter, now, to ARDC and its partners: PIDs are part of a vision of how the research information landscape should evolve that has created a global consensus, and secondly ARDC PID services are essential for the Australian research community to meet a variety of policy and practical aspirations.

2.1. PIDs and a vision of the research landscape.

A range of initiatives have emerged in recent years which articulate a vision of how the research landscape should evolve and improve. They include visions of a more open world, and one in which research evaluation takes account of a wider range of activities and responsible metrics. In many of these, PIDs are either called out directly as essential, or are implicitly needed for the vision to work.

As an example, the FAIR principles state that research data should be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. They have become a unifying banner under which many improvements to the management of research data (and information about research more generally) have been made. They recognise the value of PIDs, stating that data should have a “globally unique and eternally persistent identifier”, and that “(meta)data are retrievable by their identifiers using a standardized communications protocol.”¹

The international “cOAlition S” group of funders have established the Plan S initiative, to speed the transition to open science. Their technical advice to publishers, repositories and other systems handling research outputs explicitly demands PIDs for publications, funders, grants, researchers, and institutions. It also requires interoperable, open (as in available under a CC-0 licence) metadata linking to data, code, pre-prints and other associated outputs.²

The United Kingdom is in the process of formulating a national PID strategy. This work is being directed by UKRI in partnership with Jisc, and is based on an analysis of infrastructure needs for the UK’s ambitious open research agenda.³

Other high-level, multinational open research initiatives, such as the European Open Science Cloud⁴, are requiring the use of PIDs for data, other outputs and associated entities, with PID services being embedded in the evolving EOSC portfolio via its PID policy⁵ and projects such as Freya⁶ in which, of course, ARDC is a partner.

¹ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

² <https://www.coalition-s.org/principles-and-implementation>

³ At the time of writing, the core proposal for this strategy has not yet been published.

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

⁵ Hellström, Maggie, Heughebaert, André, Kotarski, Rachael, Manghi, Paolo, Matthews, Brian, Ritz, Raphael, ... Wittenburg, Peter. (2019, December 13). Initial Persistent Identifier (PID) policy for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (Version 1.0). Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3574203>

⁶ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en>

According to the European Commission's Turning FAIR Data into Reality report:

*“Central to the realisation of FAIR are FAIR Digital Objects, which may represent data, software or other research resources. **These digital objects must be accompanied by persistent identifiers**, metadata and contextual documentation to enable discovery, citation and reuse.*

*FAIR Digital Objects can only exist in a FAIR ecosystem, comprising key data services that are needed to support FAIR. **These include services that provide persistent identifiers**, metadata specifications, stewardship and repositories, actionable policies and Data Management Plans.”⁷*

Building on the report, representatives from the EOSC FAIR⁸ and EOSC Architecture Working Groups⁹ have joined forces to create an outline of what is meant by ‘persistent identifier’ and what the key features of PIDs are that must be present in order to support FAIR research across EOSC. The result is the draft EOSC PIDs Policy¹⁰ which has been released for public comment.

⁷ <http://doi.org/10.2777/1524>

⁸ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/fair-working-group>

⁹ <https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/working-groups/architecture-working-group>

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3574203>

2.2. PIDs and Australian requirements.

The Australian Group of Eight universities are a signatory to the Sorbonne Declaration¹¹ which specifically commits to “supporting our universities and their researchers in making data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR)”. A range of Australian research institutions, led by the Council of Australian University Librarians, have made a statement supporting FAIR Access to Australia’s Research¹². Australian NCRIS guidelines¹³ now require NCRIS facilities to work towards making the research outputs they enable FAIR.

In addition to FAIR, the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research 2018, released by the National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia, calls for institutions to “provide access to facilities for the safe and secure storage and management of research data, records and primary materials and, where possible and appropriate, allow access and reference”.

The code requires researchers to “retain clear, accurate, secure and complete records of all research including research data and primary materials. Where possible and appropriate, allow access and reference to these by interested parties.” PIDs and their associated metadata provide a practical toolkit for meeting this requirement.

The guidance in support of the code also recommends “Researchers should adhere to established national and international standards for data description and structuring to facilitate tracking of references. These standards include using Digital Object Identifiers for datasets, ORCID IDs for researchers, and standard terminology for scientific concepts.”¹⁴ Once again, this serves to emphasise the importance of the global PID network, and the fora that it contains for reaching consensus on standards and practices. Access to this network, and the ability to shape its priorities, is crucial to help Australian researchers meet the demands of modern research integrity.

¹¹ <https://www.leru.org/files/Sorbonne-declaration.pdf>

¹² <https://www.fair-access.net.au/>

¹³ <https://docs.education.gov.au/documents/ncris-2018-guidelines>

¹⁴ <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/australian-code-responsible-conduct-research-2018#download>

2.3. Why ARDC?

As part of its commitment to bringing competitive advantage to Australian researchers, ARDC has been working tirelessly to lead the charge on making data FAIR¹⁵, establishing tools and projects to help advance the management and sharing of Australian researcher data. ARDC's suite of national PID services, support, and infrastructure, combined with the Australian Access Federation's (AAF) efforts as Australian ORCID Consortium lead, are the backbone of enabling FAIR data outputs in Australia - both in the infrastructure and collections ARDC and its partners have developed and in the Australian research sector as a whole.

PIDs are a core component of ARDC services and they are captured and displayed in Research Data Australia¹⁶. ARDC is the primary national infrastructure provider of PIDs to the Australian research sector and is positioned to lead the national PID agenda across the research sector. Via the Data and Services¹⁷ portfolio ARDC provides DOIs¹⁸ (for research data, software, grey literature), RAIDs¹⁹ (for research projects), IGSNs²⁰ (for physical objects collected during the course of research), PURLs²¹ (for research grants), and Handles²² (for data and for the foundation of RAIDs). ARDC played a key role (then, as ANDS) in the formation of the Australian ORCID Consortium²³ and actively supports ORCID²⁴ and the AAF in their role as the Consortium Lead. Uptake of PID services by the sector is high (for example, 61 Australian repositories use the DOI service) and builds on historical leadership (via ANDS) in this area. Internationally, the ARDC has played a leadership role in the development of PIDs and related initiatives that leverage PIDs to track research data connections and impact.

ARDC PID services naturally rely on international PID infrastructure providers who operate within a dynamic and evolving landscape. For this reason, ARDC staff are leading or have representation on a wide range of international PID providers, groups, and initiatives, providing a significant scope and scale of involvement to promote ARDC's priorities and to influence strategies. In order to drive towards a coordinated PID ecosystem for Australia ARDC needs to continue to occupy leading roles both nationally and internationally.

PIDs are the backbone of world class research (data) infrastructure. ARDC has a history of, and experience in, providing leadership in PIDs and in offering PID services for data and related materials. There is no other organisation offering this breadth of leadership, experience and extent of PID offerings in the Australian research sector. By continuing to offer services and leadership in this area, ARDC is contributing substantially to the discovery, preservation, citation

¹⁵ <https://ardc.edu.au/news/advocating-for-fair-data-in-australia/>

¹⁶ <https://researchdata.ands.org.au/>

¹⁷ <https://ardc.edu.au/services/identifier/>

¹⁸ <https://datacite.org/doi.html>

¹⁹ <https://www.raid.org.au/>

²⁰ <http://www.igsn.org/>

²¹ <https://archive.org/services/purl/>

²² <http://handle.net/>

²³ <https://aaf.edu.au/orcid/>

²⁴ <https://orcid.org/>

and re-use of Australian research data and the ability for sector stakeholders to track the impact of this research and, by extension, ARDC infrastructure investments.

The diagram below uses a simple model of the research lifecycle to show how PIDs are intertwined with ARDC services throughout the research enterprise. For example, by the time a service is used or a dataset is created, PIDs for people, organisations and funding should already be in place and ready to connect.

As you can see, ARDC is a major player in the PID space already, both as a user and a provider. ARDC is a valued partner to some of the most important PID services (such as DataCite or ORCID) operating across the research community. PIDs are pervasive across ARDC activities, with nuances at the level of individual services and PIDs. For example, these systems are at different stages of maturity and penetration, and therefore each requires a distinctly different intervention.

2.4. Terms of engagement of the PID portfolio review

For a long-term, highly visible investment in mission-critical tools and services, it is vital to have a set of guiding principles to bring consistency and clarity to both decisions and communications. To maintain that coherent strategic approach to these interventions, the reviewer and the ARDC Data and Services team agreed on a set of five tenets to inform the review and recommendations for each service. These are:

	<p>Research is global</p> <p>Local services must use international standards wherever they are available and be an active component in global networks.</p>
	<p>Data is at risk</p> <p>Services must plan for technological obsolescence, ensure descriptive information, standards, and open technologies are used wherever possible to optimize data portability and develop international redundancies.</p>
	<p>Partnership is leadership</p> <p>No organisation or nation can solve the myriad challenges of multi-disciplinary, unstable research world alone, but in the ‘hands-on’ environment of international information infrastructures, to participate in the teams providing possible solutions is de facto to lead the pack.</p>
	<p>Diversification tames wickedness</p> <p>In an inherently ‘wicked’ environment (in which information is incomplete and feedback is often late, absent or misleading), ARDC need a wide range of partners and a mix of approaches to gain the greatest chance of identifying and managing risks early and of maintaining the right portfolio balance to support Australian research.</p>
	<p>Pick your battles</p> <p>Productive participation in global networks requires effort, resources and commitment. Be selective and choose strategic engagements which map to current or emerging organisational and community needs.</p>

These principles form a mental model to underpin the analysis of ARDC’s portfolio of PID services and activities. While all of these principles were relevant in each review, some are more significant to the recommendations which emerged. The most influential tenets are called out in the summaries below.

3. ARDC PID services: review findings and recommendations

This section breaks out each service individually and summarises the main findings of the review. Strategic values are spelled out, while the urgency, importance and degree of effort of actions are set out visually for glanceability. Recommendations are set out alongside an intervention timeline. The detailed reviews, and many concrete examples of actions to be taken, are housed in the appendices to this report.

PIDs provide a scalable toolkit for the discovery, preservation, and re-use of data. They are integral to the FAIR data principles. By smoothing interoperation and aiding citation they help us to recognise excellence wherever it is found and to understand the context and impact of our investments and their results.

As noted in the accompanying documents, PIDs have become a critical dependency for ARDC services. The majority of the PIDs discussed here are already heavily used (as per the context diagram above) and ARDC is involved with them all either as a provider, partner, or user of their services. As such, inaction is not an option for any of them. Should ARDC decide to draw back from any given PID, there will need to be time and effort invested in crafting an exit strategy and managing a transition.

The goal of this review, therefore, is to create sustainable engagements, with investment where needed to achieve a stable state of operation. Sustainability here implies reduced cost or cost neutrality wherever possible, and demonstrable return on investment in all cases. Engagement requires partnership and a visible, consistent, positive presence in the global PID community. Only by helping to set the path of PID services can one hope to stay ahead of the risks implicit in one's dependency on them.

Many of the recommendations below, therefore, are that ARDC should act now across its PID portfolio. Where appropriate, these actions include finely targeted short- to medium-term investments to mitigate risk and maximise benefit.

Note: The International Geo Sample Number (IGSN) has been placed out of scope for this review, as they are in the process of conducting a major review of their operating model. Absent the conclusions of that review, it is not possible to make an assessment of ARDC's future relationship with the initiative.

3.1. RAiD

Projects are where most academic research happens. They are a crucial source of contextual and practical information about datasets, software, and other outputs. This information is critical to the FAIRness of that data. The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is the only viable candidate for a project identifier currently on the horizon. As such, it has provoked considerable interest amongst the PID cognoscenti around the world, and ARDC is blessed with a pool of willing partners to help develop it into a fully sustainable, global service. To harness that momentum, and to preserve first-mover advantage, the RAiD review (see Appendix 1) recommends some prompt actions in 2020 to lay the foundation for a bright future for the service.

Strategic value:		
Pick your battles – ARDC has all the ingredients in place to make a global success of RAiD and benefits from a significant head start		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARDC should invest in an enlarged core team to operate and expand RAiD • Transition the existing advisory group to a formal governance board • Pilot RAiD services in multiple disciplinary etc. contexts • Build RAiD into a global network, spreading the burden and risk amongst partner ‘registration agencies’ • Work with pilot partners/registration agencies to develop a sustainable cost recovery model • Build income to sustainable levels and develop exit strategy 	

3.2. DataCite DOIs

DataCite is a vital partner for ARDC. ARDC sits on the DataCite board, and 61 repositories in the Australian network are registering DOIs for their data via DataCite services. This relationship is also at a turning point: ARDC has funded DataCite memberships for Australian research organizations up to now, but the membership model of DataCite is changing, and this means that ARDC’s role must also change to accommodate more direct connections between DataCite and its members. Such connections should include encouraging the use of DataCite’s Fabrica service for DOI registration. For the full option analyses and assessments to help to guide ARDC’s engagement with the process see Appendix 2.

Strategic value:		
Partnership is leadership – ARDC leads the Australian community in best data practices, and is advancing those practices globally		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition to new consortium model and establish Australian governance group • Collect impact case studies and examples of the benefits of DataCite DOIs and associated services (Scholix etc.) • Support the development of the Event Data service to help members track the impact of their data • Ensure members are making optimal use of DOIs and centralised DataCite services (such as Fabrica) • Educate the community in the value of DOIs and ROI of membership and establish a cost recovery model to support the consortium 	

3.3. Organisation identifiers

The Organisation identifier review (see Appendix 3) concluded that of the available candidates, the ROR offers the best fit for our community's needs. This is a fledgling initiative, whose leadership has reached out to ARDC for support. RDA already plans to use the ROR API to identify organisations in dataset descriptions, so ARDC should manage this dependency by actively helping ROR to reach sustainability. ARDC should join the global coalition of ROR supporters and help to ensure that the service grows and meets the needs of Australian organisations.

Strategic value:		
Research is global – an international research organisation registry increases the breadth of information that can be linked to datasets etc.		
Data is at risk – accurately identifying the organisations responsible for the creation and curation of data is critical to its longevity		
Diversification tames wickedness – a dedicated research organisation PID will improve data quality and availability		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARDC needs to identify organisations within and without the research space: services such as Research Data Australia should support ABNs alongside ROR. • ROR needs to develop to bring optimal value to our partners. ARDC should make a multi-pronged investment in ROR: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ One-off contribution or recurring project funding for ROR. ○ Providing development or other practical resources to ROR to accelerate its journey to sustainability. ○ Implementing ROR IDs in our services, and support and encourage the Australian research community in start using them. ○ Establish a benefits realisation program to show the value of ROR to the Australian community 	

3.4. Grant IDs

ARDC has been providing PURLs to the ARC to act as grant identifiers for some time. While this works, it has limited uptake and is not incorporated into funding acknowledgements in any programmatic way. A global DOI registration agency, Crossref, has established a grant ID service which is designed to connect to the submission systems of their >12,000 publisher and repository members. Given this level of adoption, the grant identifier review (see Appendix 4) recommends that ARDC pilot this new initiative in its own role as a funder. This pilot should have the goal to maximise the discovery and accuracy of tracking and analysing the impact of ARDC’s investments.

Strategic value:		
Diversification tames wickedness – working with an emerging global standard gives the best chance of understanding impact		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
<p>2020</p> <p>2021</p> <p>2022</p> <p>2023</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate grant IDs into ARDC award workflows and share metadata via Crossref • Integrate grant ID linking tools in RDA and in grantee repository systems • Explore possible synergies with other ARDC PIDs and services • Evaluate the costs and benefits of grant IDs and their value in impact tracking and analysis 	

3.5. Instrument IDs

Instruments are integral to the creation, nature, and meaning of research data. ARDC has been a major player in the evolution of good practice in identifying instruments, both nationally and internationally, and already supports services which could be extended to enable optimal adoption of instrument PIDs across Australia. The Instrument PIDs review (see Appendix 5) found that ARDC’s leadership in this space has positioned it well to implement emerging developments, such as DataCite’s plans to include instrument metadata in their schema, but that work needs to be done to ensure equitable access to their benefits.

Strategic value:		
Pick your battles – this is an area where ARDC is uniquely placed at the juncture of several initiatives to deliver these PIDs to our partners		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARDC should work with both the Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group and DataCite’s Metadata Working Group to influence and accelerate the deployment of the schema • build a central instrument portal in Research Data Australia • provide specifications and support for organisations and platforms seeking to implement instrument DOIs 	

3.6. Handle

Handles are an essential component of ARDC’s PID portfolio, and underpin several opportunities for growth and sustainability. Continuing to offer Handle services will contribute to the diversity and balance of ARDC’s portfolio, but only if action is taken to improve the resilience and scalability of those services. The Handle review (see Appendix 6) found that the current underpinnings of the Handle system at ARDC do not reflect its importance to the sector, and do not reflect likely levels of future usage and growth.

Strategic value:		
Pick your battles – ARDC can reinforce its own service portfolio and that of its partners at a relatively low cost in effort and resources		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARDC should join ePIC to assure the continuity of Handle resolution and minting services • ARDC should transition away from the reliance on donated infrastructure, and transition to an enterprise solution for primary service provision • the Data and Services team should explore ways that Handle-based services could be coupled to rationalise costs. • the Data and Services team should investigate the level and sophistication of Handle adoption across the sector and plan for the need to transition institutional Handle servers in-house as bulk transfers 	

3.7. ORCID

ORCID iDs have emerged as the global de facto standard for researcher identification. ARDC has led the Australian community in adopting and integrating ORCID iDs, and was instrumental in the creation of the national ORCID consortium, which is managed by AAF. That said, after 4 years, the consortium has not yet succeeded in delivering all of the benefits envisaged at its launch. The ORCID support review (see Appendix 7) identifies gaps in adoption and usage, and unexploited opportunities to enhance the ecosystem. It recommends that ARDC should leverage AAF’s work in evaluating the maturity of ORCID adoption in Australia, and build upon that evidence to optimise its own service interactions with members and with ORCID itself to position Australia at the leading edge of ORCID integration and to optimise the benefits to organisations, funders and researchers alike.

Strategic value:		
Data is at risk – inconsistent coverage, adoption, and integration mean information is getting lost, and errors are introduced		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARDC as a key partner in the Australian ORCID consortium should work closely with AAF and consortium members to support benefits realisation activities • ARDC as a service provider, information aggregator, and PID provider in its own right, should develop an ORCID benefits optimization strategy • provide quantitative evidence of the benefits of widespread ORCID adoption in Australia 	

3.8. AGLDWG

The Australian Government Linked Data Working Group has approached ARDC with a request for help in stabilising their service and extending it to the research sector. The potential of an identification infrastructure that serves both research and government at the state and federal level could be significant. It could help policy makers to assess the evidence presented to them by Australian researchers, and allow researchers to dig deeper and more easily into information resources generated by the government. The AGLDWG recommendations (see Appendix 8) found that providing a place in ARDC’s portfolio for the identifier would also provide more diversity of approach, and could generate insights into community needs and practice which will be instrumental in evolving ARDC services and supporting robust research practice.

Strategic value:		
Diversification tames wickedness – the AGLDWG approach to identifiers is distinct from others in use and is worth exploring		
Urgency:	Importance:	Effort:
Timeline:	Actions Needed:	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adopt and stabilise the AGLDWG service • Use AGLDWG as an opportunity and means to experiment with more diverse approaches to identifiers • Explore the commonalities of approach and functionality with other PID services 	

4. Conclusions.

Persistent identifiers are embedded in modern research workflows and services, and ARDC is no exception. Where ARDC is genuinely exceptional is in its determination to manage the risk of PID dependencies by active and constructive engagement with the technical and social underpinnings of the global PID network. This engagement brings significant benefits to ARDC's work, in terms of horizon-scanning, best practice, and practical support in solving thorny problems.

The cost of using and extending PID services is not trivial. The staff resources and development expertise required are, however, best seen as an investment in the robustness, interoperability, and, ultimately, sustainability of ARDCs infrastructure. PIDs enable ARDC services to form part of global discovery networks, projecting Australian research excellence on the international stage. They offer an opportunity to enrich metadata, and to automate steps in data curation and analysis workflows, improving the efficiency and user experience of ARDC services. Furthermore, this review has identified routes to cost recovery for several ARDC PID investments, meaning that over their viable lifetime they should doubly reward the investments proposed.

The advantage of the years of effort already put into PID integrations by ARDC and its precursor organisations is that there are solid foundations upon which to build. ARDC services are for the most part ready to capitalise on the synergies between PIDs for people, organisations, samples, instruments, projects, software, grants, places, things and, of course, data. Some activities can be shared with partners and others can be streamlined. The portfolio should be deployed consistently across the Australian research landscape, and taken as a whole it is a compelling offering.

In strengthening and improving the integration of PIDs across ARDC, and its partners, the team should be ever-mindful of the ways in which new interactions between these PIDs and services could further enhance the utility of research data, and enable previously difficult or impossible tasks to be completed. By critically assessing the workflows and infrastructures upon which the research enterprise stands or falls, PID-enabled improvements can be brought to bear on pain points, inefficiencies and risk such as data loss.

While there are practical and business challenges to overcome, the portfolio is ready to support the most essential entities in the research lifecycle. ARDC can assure its members and the Australian research community that it is building and enabling an innovative, scalable, and responsive PID-optimised research information network.

Declaration of interests.

I have the following interests to declare in the subjects of this review:

- I was employed by ORCID in a number of roles from 2014 to 2019
- I have partnered with DataCite on projects, and worked with several members of the current DataCite staff in various roles since 2012
- I sit on the RAiD advisory board
- I was employed by Crossref to help launch their grant ID service in 2019
- I conducted research into research community requirements of an organisation identifier and analysed the landscape of organisation identifier provision as part of the precursor project to ROR from 2016 to 2017

Josh Brown, April 2020.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) review

Josh Brown, February 2020

Introduction.

The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) offers a flexible, scalable toolkit to connect datasets to people, software, organisations, funding, outputs, instruments and many other entities essential to the FAIRness of data. Accurate and reliable records of the means and context of data creation are vital to assessing the integrity of our research evidence base. Systematically linking these entities offers us the greatest chance of capturing impact and thereby demonstrating the excellence of both the research itself and the network of systems and services that underpin it.

RAiD is a compound object identifier. Established PIDs, like Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) are generally used to identify and describe discrete entities, like a journal article, or a data file. For complex entities, like an artist's portfolio, or a collaborative activity, these PIDs are useful, but can't be used to identify the 'envelope'. Instead, they identify its contents.

For the purposes of research integrity, project management, career reporting, impact assessment and other critical administrative and analytical functions, understanding the 'envelope' can be as important as understanding any of the individual entities contained within it. Knowing what is in there is vital, of course, but that knowledge is only partially meaningful if you can't say how those things relate to one another. These relationships add a layer of complexity that most single-entity PIDs just can't capture.

While this is a well understood need, solutions have been slow in coming. Back in the 2000s, protocols like the Open Archive Initiative's standard for Object Re-use and Exchange (OAI-ORE)²⁵ (a cousin to the still widely-used OAI-PMH) were developed, but have gained little traction. Perhaps they were ahead of their time, or were too complex. Perhaps they did not articulate their use case or value proposition effectively. For whatever reason, the community still facing the same problem in 2020 as it did in 2006. How to knit together disparate entities that have a connection to one another?

A significant group of identifier experts and enthusiasts have concluded that RAiD offers just such a solution to a particularly pressing challenge: identifying projects. Projects matter because they are where much research actually happens. Understanding the make-up of a project is vital

²⁵ <https://www.openarchives.org/ore/>

if one is to map out all the possible impacts that arise from the inputs, activities, and outputs that make it up. The problem until now has been that projects are complex, compound entities, and there has not been a viable standard to identify and describe them.

Background.

RAiD was established in 2017 with an original remit to function as an actionable data management record. It was originally a project funded by Research Data Services as part of the Data Life Cycle Framework Project. The vision was of an identifier (a Handle²⁶) with associated metadata which would capture the individuals, organisations, funding grants, equipment and other research entities linked to the creation, curation, and preservation of a dataset.

It quickly became clear that the RAiD design could operate very well as a project identifier, since capturing the entities, roles, and relationships around a uniquely identified activity profile can both reflect and complement traditional project management tools. In the context of research data, it also provides a record of the context of and contributors to a dataset which is vital for research integrity and reproducibility.

When RAiD was presented to the identifier community at PIDapalooza in January 2018, there was an immediate consensus that it was a highly effective and desirable solution to the need for project identifiers. Interest has remained high in the intervening months and years.

Where is RAiD now?

RAiD is in active use in 7 Australian organisations at the time of writing, with a further 17 organisations holding keys to the system. 5,366 live RAiDs have been minted. RAiD records hold associations with a range of other identifier systems, including ORCID iDs for people, ROR, ISNI and GRID IDs for organisations, DOIs for datasets and articles and Handles for instruments.

RAiD is in the process of being certified as an official international standard with ISO. The process takes 36 months (although it can extend to 48 months if needed) and has been underway since May 2018. The official standard should be published in May 2021.

As mentioned above, there is a lot of interest in RAiD. Project PIDs have been identified as a very high priority for the research community. In workshops held in 2017 and 2018 at dedicated events and alongside the FORCE and PIDapalooza conferences, project IDs were consistently ranked near the top of the list of current and emerging PIDs that the community felt were essential. (Others included PIDs for people, organisations, grants and outputs (including pre-prints and data.)

²⁶ <https://www.handle.net/>

This sense of urgency is borne out in the range of stakeholders around the world actively seeking to work with RAiD. Jisc in the UK are keen to explore pilot implementations of RAiD across several disciplinary communities (including the arts, medicine and physical sciences at present, although a partner working in the social sciences is being sought). In the Netherlands, the national funder and SURF are working on a pilot using RAiDs to track funded High Performance Computing projects. In the United States, Oak Ridge National Laboratory and the Howard Hughes Medical Institute have both separately sought to work with RAiD.

The potential benefits and risks of RAiD.

RAiD meets an established community need. It builds on existing ARDC services (especially the Handle service), and offers ways to bring entities within Research Data Australia, international systems, and institutional systems together in a defined context. This value is apparent to the 24 Australian research organisations that have already begun work on RAiD integrations, and to the multiple international partners seeking to pilot RAiD in their communities. However, there are risks and negative factors which could affect RAiD on its current trajectory. The SWOT analysis below highlights some of these.

In opposition to its potential value, note that since launching in 2017 RAiD has only accrued 7 live integrations. This is hardly explosive growth. It also has very limited capacity at the moment for technical, product, or business development, which will hamper ongoing scaling and

expansion of the service. This capacity to scale is absolutely critical to successful PID services. They derive a lot of their value and credibility from high levels of adoption and so must provide a system that is user-friendly and reliable in order to attract and retain the users that help them to deliver their goals.

With 17 Australian organisations and several well-resourced international partners keen to build on RAiD, it should be possible to de-risk expansion somewhat, with additional investments and resources coming in from other organisations. Pilots should also help to articulate the natural workflows and business process owners for RAiD. As the person is the logical owner for an ORCID record, so the project coordinator is the logical owner for a RAiD record. This brings research offices and funders to the fore as vital stakeholders in refining the value proposition for RAiD and developing the interfaces and tools to leverage that value.

Australia is seen as punching above its weight in the PIDs category, which means that RAiD has gathered a lot of attention in the PID community. This means that RAiD could easily become a high-impact global service, strengthening ARDC's standing and partnerships. Other project PID initiatives have been put on hold since RAiD has been positioned as the most plausible advanced candidate to fill this gap in PID provision, which has consolidated ARDC's first mover advantage in this space. If RAiD does not move to seize this advantage, however, by making significant visible progress in 2020, it risks arriving at the next cycle of PID-community gatherings (FORCE, PIDapalooza and so on) with nothing new to report. Having made such a big splash with RAiD it could seriously harm ARDC's credibility if nothing substantive is delivered. RAiD is too valuable to languish as 'vapourware'.

If the existing support from the University of Queensland and ARDC is not leveraged to develop a long-term sustainable PID service, ARDC risks wasting more than the money that has been invested and committed in scoping and laying the foundations for RAiD. In the absence of tangible progress, others will step forward to fill the gap, and their solutions may diverge from the approach or technologies used by RAiD. If this occurs, at some point after 2021 another solution will be positioned to capitalise on the global demand for project PIDs and whatever is developed is unlikely to be shaped to the needs of Australian research in the way that RAiD has. If it is built for the needs of a particular community or infrastructure and/or is not backward compatible with RAiD, ARDC will be forced to do the heavy lifting of ensuring that it serves its members and service users.

Building out a new, global infrastructure does not come without risk. ARDC will need to generate resources to support the work, and take on the burden of overseeing a large and diverse stakeholder community. This offers reputational risks which could rival those of doing nothing unless they are carefully managed. Any strategy to maximise the impact and returns of existing investments in RAiD will need to mitigate these risks and ensure that in growing the user base, ARDC also spreads the load of service development and sustainability.

Recommendations.

Given the risks of doing nothing, it is better to build RAiD up, and to actively seek partnerships and business opportunities to mitigate the risks of action. Pilot partners are ready to invest in their own architecture to provide RAiD services locally. This offers the option of a Registration Agency (RA) model, similar to that used by DOI or ISNI to enable them to scale and serve defined communities of practice.

This review recommends that **ARDC should invest to build RAiD into a global network, spreading the burden of product development, with RAs managing relationships and registrations and affording some flexibility in the evolution of RAiD services and metadata.**

Internationalising RAiD ensures that the solution of choice for Australian research organisations will be compatible with their global collaborators, and gives the best chance of real persistence for RAiDs. It aligns with ARDC's terms of engagement with PIDs, in that **Research is global**. The conversation around RAiD has been international from the get go, and it aligns with the nature of the entities RAiD seeks to identify: projects. Research collaborations are international, and funders and employers are keen to understand international activities of Australian researchers.

Furthermore, the PID systems RAiD depends on are themselves international. Having set out to achieve standard status, RAiD has attention and support globally. Operating at an international scale will be crucial to achieving sustainability and coverage. A global market offers a potential funding stream to put RAiD on a long-term cost recovery basis, and many of the challenges of project PIDs across disciplines will require help and input from global communities and experts.

As highlighted above, the risks of doing nothing are real. The principle that ARDC should **pick your battles** applies here, in that there is a real and well-defined need for this service, and the potential costs of re-engineering RAiD or starting from scratch are unknown but could be substantial, notwithstanding the loss of sunk costs, future investment and community standing.

Picking one's battles implies knowing how far one is willing to go in the fight. The goal of the RAiD strategy should be full cost-recovery. **ARDC should establish a business model that ensures RAs can recoup their costs whilst contributing to the sustainability of the central service.** Since ARDC/UQ are committed to hosting RAiD for 10 years, this offers comparatively luxurious time to support the evolution of such a business. At the end of the current commitment, assuming RAiD achieves break-even, then ARDC will be presented with a ready-made exit strategy, as it will have the option to spin RAiD out into an independent organisation or foundation.

The growing pool of pilot partners (and candidate RAs) provides a foundation on which to establish the necessary formal governance structures for the service. In taking ownership of this network, ARDC can follow the principle that **partnership is leadership. The next step should**

be to activate the existing RAiD advisory group with the aim to transition it to a formal governance board. The group should be mobilised to create a task-limited working group to look at RA and business models, and to support the RAiD team in setting up pilots with supportive potential RAs.

RAiD pilots will need to work across disciplines as well as borders to demonstrate adaptability of the platform and metadata. For example, it should take on the needs of the arts community, which is often seen as 'too hard' by platform providers, with its diverse group of outputs, extensive collaboration and cross-sector working. They are frequently underserved by 'publication-centric' systems and reporting exercises. This community offers a chance to adapt RAiD to create portfolios, linking outputs in various guises to records, funding, institutions, people and so on. This also builds on the origin of RAiD as a 'group ID' concept. At the same time, there are defined challenges in the medical sciences, such as shared infrastructures and the difficulty of tracking high-throughput projects with high collaborator turnover often at several removes from the funder. The UK's National Institute for Health Research has a demonstration token and are keen to participate as a pilot partner.

To deliver this program, **ARDC should invest in an enlarged core team to operate and expand RAiD.** A global project of this scale requires multiple skill sets, and strong leadership.

The immediate need is for a senior ARDC champion for the project. This Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) should recruit additional staff to accelerate the growth of the service, ensure that RAiD can scale and is responsive to the data coming in from the pilots, and to support the SRO and board in building and cementing partnerships and modelling different cost recovery options. This will require three distinct areas of expertise:

1. *Community development manager* - responsible for partnerships and business development.
2. *Product manager* - processing the inputs from the community and balancing them against the needs/limitations of the service to future-proof the platform and make it as accessible and usable as possible.
3. *Technical lead* - building out the code, architecture and service in line with modern standards and to work with the RAs to ensure they maintain compatibility with the RAiD core.

Each of these roles mirrors functions to be found in other major PID providers. 3 EFT staff is a relatively modest team for an operation of this scale, but it will be augmented by inputs from pilot partners and RAs, meaning the service can scale without ARDC shouldering all the risks and operational burden.

Finally, **ARDC should aim to have these actions completed or under way by the end of Q3 2020**, meaning that there will be concrete, palpable developments to report to the global PID community by the FORCE conference and Research Data Alliance plenary in October 2020 and

PIDapalooza in January 2021. This is vital to preserve the first mover advantage ARDC currently enjoys, and to build momentum and appetite for participation in RAiD.

Appendix 2: DataCite DOIs options

Author's note : These papers were prepared in partnership with ARDC staff in response to the evolving business model of DataCite. This evolution has stepped up several gears as leadership at DataCite has changed, and a renewed urgency has been placed on sustainability. The original options paper, presented below, explored the rationale for ARDC continuing to support the Australian community in their use of DataCite DOIs for their data, software and other outputs. It concluded that the best approach was to minimise the disruption of changes to the sector, and to avoid disincentivising researchers and their host organisations from maximising their use of PIDs for data.

The European Commission-funded Freya project found that DOIs and Handles are the two most widely used PIDs for data and associated entities²⁷. Both approaches are supported by ARDC, which is sensible. DOIs are a form of Handle, but they come with a host of sector-specific enhancements, including metadata schemas, registries, discovery tools and more. These tools are becoming indispensable, and are increasingly foundational in mapping research graphs²⁸ and uncovering impacts beyond traditional data citation. As such, ARDC should be encouraging the use of DataCite DOIs wherever possible.

In light of this, the recommendations of this review are intended to smooth the transition to organisations paying for their own DataCite membership, with ARDC as consortium lead. Concrete steps to be taken to prepare for this transition include: raising awareness of the value and purpose of DataCite DOIs; supporting the development of tools to track the impact of data, such as the Event Data²⁹ service and Scholix³⁰; highlighting case studies of benefits derived from the use of DOIs for data; and evaluating cost recovery options to contain costs to members and to minimise potential drop-outs from the consortium.

²⁷ Ferguson, C, McEntrye, J, Bunakov, V, Lambert, S, van der Sandt, S, Kotarski, R, Stewart, S, MacEwan, A, Fenner, M, Cruse, P, van Horik, R, Dohna, T, Koop-Jacobsen, K, Schindler, U, McCafferty S. (2018). D3.1 Survey of Current PID Services Landscape (Version 1). Available online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324295>

²⁸ Aryani, A, Poblet, M, Unsworth, K, Wang, J, Evans, B, Devaraju, A, et al. (2018). "A research graph dataset for connecting research data repositories using RD-Switchboard". *Sci. Data* 5:180099. Available online at: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.99>

²⁹ <https://datacite.org/eventdata.html>

³⁰ <http://www.scholix.org/>

ARDC DOI service options paper

Natasha Simons and Josh Brown, September 2019 (revised October 2019)

Executive summary

ARDC have supported Australian research organisations in their use of DataCite to register DOIs for datasets and other content. DataCite are now changing their membership model, with 2020 as a transition year. ARDC therefore has the opportunity to review its engagement with DataCite and its role as an intermediary as part of this process.

There are various ways that ARDC can facilitate DOI usage in Australian repositories and data centres. Given that the use of persistent identifiers for research entities (content, people, organisations etc.) is widely recognised as a good thing, this review assumes that the continued use of DOIs for datasets and related content types is beneficial. The questions that remain to be considered are whether or not ARDC should continue to support the Australian research sector in using DataCite DOI, what form any such support should take, and what costs and risks would be incurred as a result of any action (or withdrawal from this activity).

This paper outlines the nature and reasons for the changes to DataCite's model, and explains the costs and unknowns. It then sets out and evaluates 6 options, from 'cease all engagement' to 'provide access to DataCite DOIs as a core ARDC activity', with variant options such as 'use another DOI registration agency'. It explores the financial and reputational risks to ARDC of each course of action, as well as the likely scale of benefits or costs to the sector.

Recommendations

This review recommends option 1 (below) in which ARDC forms a national DataCite consortium and covers the membership and registration costs for the sector.

In so doing, ARDC will provide the greatest possible stability for the sector, and gain the greatest opportunity to influence developments at DataCite. It also offers the best chance to actively manage the evolution of this situation by taking maximum control of the relationship with DataCite.

The primary value for current DataCite users is that no one has to change their behaviour, no one is disincentivised from using DOIs for content (or perversely using fewer DOIs for content), and possible unintended consequences are minimised. Should the situation change in the future, with costs rising, budgets reducing, or an alternative consortium lead emerging, ARDC will have time to arrange an orderly transition and communicate effectively.

The known financial costs are relatively low, and the benefits to ARDC are significant: Reputationally, ARDC is supporting 61 organisations in following best practice with their

research data management; ensuring a level playing field for small organisations who otherwise would not be able to offer DOIs for content to their researchers; guaranteeing stability and consistency for members and partners. Financially, it offers the best chance of containing costs in future, and incentivising organisations to join ARDC. Practically, it ensures a degree of consistency and interoperability in Australian research data management which aids the current service offering and provides a better foundation for future innovation. It is also consistent and predictable and avoids arbitrary tiering and administration involved in monitoring and managing transitions above and below boundaries.

If ARDC does adopt this recommendation, it should come with clear review points and under an ongoing watching brief. DataCite has a new Executive Director and the membership model is subject to changes as it continues to evolve. It is not completely clear yet what 2021 costs will be, so the first review point should be mid-2020 when more data is available. From then on, close engagement with DataCite should guarantee sufficient warning to re-appraise options as new costs and opportunities appear. This should give ARDC plenty of time to review changes, and to transition smoothly to another model if needed. Assuming no significant changes, ARDC should review costs of DOI registration annually, and evaluate this consortium after 2 to 3 years. Crucially, ARDC should communicate to the sector that it is providing continuity and managing this risk on their behalf.

Background: New DataCite Membership Model

Previously, DataCite membership distinguished between Members, Providers, Clients, and Consortia. According to DataCite, this “led to confusion among organizations about whether or not they are a DataCite Member³¹”. Therefore they now distinguish three membership categories: Member-only, Direct Member, and Consortium Member.

Member-only: do not mint DOIs; participate in DataCite collaboration and/or governance

Direct-member: mint DOIs; “an organization that works with one or more repositories within their immediate organization”.

Consortium member: group of like-minded organizations, composed of two or more non-profit organizations that are under different administrative structures, that have come together to collectively participate in DataCite’s community and governance activities and use DataCite’s DOI services.

DataCite are encouraging all organizations that are registering DOIs to become Direct Members of DataCite so that they can actively participate in DataCite’s community and contribute to achieving its goals³². Additionally, DataCite are keen to emphasise the key role

³¹ Blog: [The DataCite Membership Model](#), 26 August 2019

³² [DataCite Membership Model](#)

played by repositories and are updating their terminology in line with this: the old “clients” terminology has been replaced with “repositories”.

Timelines: 2019 is the preparation year for changes to the DataCite Membership Model, 2020 the transition year and 2021 the execution year. During the preparation year, there will be changes to Fabrica, “clients” will be re-named “repositories” and contracts will be cancelled where appropriate. During the transition year there will be transfers and onboarding. During the execution year, invoices will be raised accordingly with the new model.

Implications for ARDC

As a (using the old terminology) “Provider” of DataCite DOIs *for organisations outside of the ARDC*, DataCite have asked ARDC to consider and decide how to transition to the new membership model. They have specifically asked ARDC to indicate the following:

1. Will ARDC be creating one or more consortiums?
2. Which organisations will be a member of which consortium?
3. Which organisation will be the consortium lead?
4. Which repositories belong to which organizations within the consortium?
5. Do any of the organisations that ARDC currently work with plan to become a direct DataCite member?

According to DataCite, the definition of a consortium is as follows:

A consortium is a group of like-minded organizations that have come together to collectively participate in DataCite’s community and governance activities and use DataCite’s DOI services. A consortium is composed of two or more non-profit organizations that are under different administrative structures. Consortia are generally located in a single country or subject based. Organizations within a consortium can work with one or more repositories.

Source: [DataCite Membership Model](#) p.3

Trisha Cruse (the former Executive Director of DataCite) advised ARDC that:

DataCite staff proposed to the DataCite Board to temporarily waive the fees for organizations that create less than 100 DOIs annually. The Board approved this proposal. This has an impact on your member fees. The DOI service fees will be waived until a more permanent fee structure for small organizations is developed and approved by the Executive Board and DataCite members. This only pertains to existing clients of members transitioning to member model - we will not offer this arrangement to newcomers.

Current DataCite membership model costs

- Total data centres in production = 59 (including ARDC)
- Total registered data centres = 68 clients (including test)
- Total DOIs minted through ARDC = 287,981 (as at 18 Jan 2019)

ARDC's 2019 DataCite DOI membership costs are provided here for comparison purposes:

- Invoice 20190019 - DataCite membership fee for 2019 (2,000€) - JIRA Ref# SD-140433
- Invoice 20190020 - Service fee for 2019 (12,000€) - JIRA Ref# SD-140432
= 14, 000 EUR
= \$22, 775 AUD (approx)

New DataCite membership model cost estimate

DataCite have provided the ARDC with a cost estimate amounting to 18, 500 Euro which is **approximately \$30, 000 AUD.**

This is a substantially discounted amount. Based on the previous year's data provided by DataCite, if ARDC were to pay in full, the amount would be as follows (and this is a minimum bound on the total costs, as it assumes that the sub 100 DOIs per annum service fee continues to be waived):

Category	Based on	Total fee in EUR
Membership	Standard fee	2, 000
Repository fee	51+ category	10, 000
DOI fee	35 members at sub 100 DOIs per annum	0
	22 members at 101-10, 000 DOIs per annum (500 EUR each)	11, 000
	2 members at 10, 001 to 100, 00 DOIs per annum (2000 EUR each)	4, 000
	1 member at 100, 001 plus DOIs per annum (3, 000 EUR each)	3, 000
TOTAL IN EURO		30, 000
TOTAL EST. IN AUD	61 organisations for approx. 72, 460 DOIs per annum (which equates to about 67 cents per DOI including membership and services)	\$48, 500 AUD

Options

Option 1: Form an ARDC-led Consortium and ARDC cover all costs

Pros:

- Sector continues to have DOI minting and service costs covered by ARDC
- ARDC leads and represents the interests of an Australian sector-wide consortium
- Sector does not have to adjust DOI minting behaviour in order to meet DataCite fee structure
- If offered as an 'optional extra' to ARDC membership, with guaranteed funding for a given number of years, it encourages uptake of the membership offer, and early adopters will derive maximum value from the freebie (61 candidate organisations are registering DataCite DOIs at time of writing)
- Offers consistent and transparent means of engaging with DataCite for all Australian research organisations (large and small).

Cons:

- All costs borne by ARDC
- Is at odds with DataCite's preference for direct membership
- Sustainability not guaranteed beyond the lifespan of the ARDC (although this proposal gives time to develop exit strategies)

Risks:

- DataCite fees will increase (N.B. DataCite cannot afford to lose members with dramatic increases, and will have to make small changes with advance warning)
- DataCite may change membership model again and Consortium may not be an option
- The number of DOIs minted through the ARDC-led Consortium could change significantly e.g. a sharp increase could lead to rising costs (N.B. The number is highly unlikely to decrease significantly)
- Reliance of the sector on the ARDC for leadership, representation and provision of service
- Sector does not see the cost the ARDC is covering and takes the DOI service for granted

Costs:

- Estimate \$30, 000 AUD in 2020 and potentially up to \$48, 500 in 2021

Option 2: Form an ARDC-led Consortium and pass all costs onto sector

Pros:

- ARDC leads the formation of the Australian sector-wide consortium
- Sector does not have to adjust DOI minting behaviour in order to meet DataCite fee structure
- Improves sustainability beyond the lifespan of the ARDC

Cons:

- Individual institutions need to make a decision about joining a Consortium with a fee component
- Individual institutions may decide that the Return on Investment is not enough to pay the Consortium membership fee and may cease minting DOIs for data
- Is at odds with DataCite's preference for direct membership
- Sustainability not guaranteed beyond the lifespan of the ARDC
- Administrative overhead costs for ARDC in managing payments

Risks:

- DataCite fees will increase
- DataCite will change membership model again and Consortium may not be an option
- The number of DOIs minted through the ARDC-led Consortium change significantly e.g. sharp increase which could lead to rising costs
- the reputation of ARDC as a gateway to best open science practice will take a small hit

Costs:

- Based on all current institutions using the ARDC service all joining the Consortium the estimate is \$30, 000 AUD in 2020 and potentially up to \$48, 500 in 2021
- Administrative overhead of analysis and invoicing and managing payments etc.

Option 3: Form an ARDC-led and subsidised Consortium for small players with an unknown cost boundary in the future

Pros:

- Small players (sub 100 DOIs per annum per institution) continue to have DOI minting and service costs covered by ARDC
- ARDC leads and represents the interests of an Australian sector-wide consortium of small players
- Small players do not have to adjust DOI minting behaviour in order to meet DataCite fee structure

Cons:

- Larger players (over 100 DOIs per annum) are outside of the Consortium
- All Consortium costs borne by ARDC
- Is at odds with DataCite's preference for direct membership
- Sustainability not guaranteed beyond the lifespan of the ARDC
- Reduced incentive for small players to increase DOI minting beyond 100 per annum
- Majority of DOI minters are outside of the Consortium
- Administrative overhead could be non-trivial

Risks:

- DataCite fees will increase

- DataCite will change membership model again and Consortium may not be an option
- The number of DOIs minted through the ARDC-led Consortium change significantly e.g. sharp increase which could lead to rising costs
- Reliance of the sector on the ARDC for leadership, representation and provision of service
- Small players do not see the cost the ARDC is covering and take the DOI service for granted

Costs:

- Estimate \$13, 000 AUD in 2020 based on membership fee (2, 000 EUR) + repository fee (35 repositories at 6, 000 EUR)

Option 4: Form an ARDC-led and subsidised Consortium for the majority (small to medium) players

Pros:

- Majority of institutions (up to 10, 000 DOIs per annum per institution) continue to have DOI minting and service costs covered by ARDC
- ARDC leads and represents the interests of an Australian sector-wide consortium of small players
- Majority of institutions do not have to adjust DOI minting behaviour in order to meet DataCite fee structure

Cons:

- Larger players (over 10, 000 DOIs per annum per institution) are outside of the Consortium
- All Consortium costs borne by ARDC
- Is at odds with DataCite's preference for direct membership
- Sustainability not guaranteed beyond the lifespan of the ARDC
- Reduced incentive for medium players to increase DOI minting beyond 10,000 per annum
- Administrative overhead could be non-trivial

Risks:

- DataCite fees will increase
- DataCite will change membership model again and Consortium may not be an option
- The number of DOIs minted through the ARDC-led Consortium change significantly e.g. sharp increase which could lead to rising costs
- Reliance of the sector on the ARDC for leadership, representation and provision of service
- Consortium members do not see the cost the ARDC is covering and take the DOI service for granted

Costs:

- Estimate \$37, 050 AUD in 2021 based on membership fee (2, 000 EUR) + repository fee (51+ repositories at 10, 000 EUR) + DOI fee (22 members at 11, 000 EUR)

Option 5: ARDC ceases to offer DOIs to the sector

Pros:

- Reduction of service costs for ARDC
- Sector decides whether to form a Consortium or go down direct-member route (could be an organic, more strongly supported entity)

Cons:

- Damages the discoverability of Australian data and content
- cedes ARDC's current 'seat at the high table'
- Encourages fragmentation of the ecosystem
- Sector decision on whether to form a Consortium or go down direct-member route is by no means guaranteed and could take years to reach consensus
- ARDC no longer leading internationally in the identifier space

Risks:

- Encourages intercession by closed/corporate players to fill newly created gap in the market
- Reputational risk for ARDC both national and international
- Can no longer capitalise

Costs:

- Minimum (ARDC will need to power down the DOI service)

Option 6: ARDC DOI Service is provided via CrossRef via sponsorship or as a Registration Agency (RA) in its own right

Pros:

- Provides greater control over service and future costs
- Replicates models used in Europe (mEDRA) and APac (JALC etc.)
- Gives unified access to services for articles, datasets, theses, preprints etc plus grants

Cons:

- Relatively expensive
- Consolidates services around a single provider with a publisher-dominated community model (dilutes influence)
- Risks damage to strategic relationship with DataCite

Risks:

- Unknown relationships and diluted influence cede control of developments
- Non-data focussed entity dilutes the utility of DIs for the sector

Costs:

- If establishing an RA from scratch, costs could be high (administration and due diligence alone will be comparatively costly)
- If using Crossref, membership costs will depend on the turnover of each organisation, but registration costs alone will exceed AU\$105,400 per annum.

Overall considerations

The evidence is clear that DOIs are a crucial tool for data management. Of the persistent identifiers available, DOIs are most used for data and articles, according to evidence gathered by the Freya project. DOIs underpin Scholix and other initiatives, are already embedded in many links to repositories (via, for example, the range of DataCite plugins for repository platforms), and can also be used for a range of scholarly outputs beyond data.

Globally, ARDC's peers use DataCite DOIs. ARDC should be encouraging and facilitating its partners in following community best practice wherever that is clearly established. Research itself is a global activity, and plugging into an established global information network, with rich metadata and downstream services makes simple, practical sense.

The repeated con "Is at odds with DataCite's preference for direct membership" is ambivalent – practically speaking, DataCite will not otherwise get the level of adoption that they will achieve via the consortium, and this gives ARDC a chance as consortium lead to promote engagement with DataCite in a way that would otherwise be impossible. Other opportunities to boost direct engagement are to encourage member institutions to use DataCite's centralised infrastructure for DOI and metadata registration, Fabrica³³. If members move to this service, then it would be possible to decommission ARDC's own DataCite DOI minting service, helping to offset additional consortium costs.

The context of the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) emphasises sector-wide service provision that both addresses researcher needs (by bolstering the creation, management and citation of datasets) and simultaneously supports "related end-user needs, including industry, Government and other end users"³⁴ (by aiding the discovery and reusability of data). While ARDC is an Australian response to these needs, it is a pragmatic necessity to incorporate international connections, and so the portfolio should naturally include access to DataCite's DOI infrastructure.

In summary, ARDC has few, if any, other options to provide a consistent 'PID foundation' for the sector, and a direct, maximal engagement offers the best chances of managing the risks that can be foreseen, and anticipating those that have yet to emerge.

³³ <https://doi.datacite.org/>

³⁴ <https://www.education.gov.au/national-collaborative-research-infrastructure-strategy-ncris>

Appendix 3: Organisation Identifiers in ARDC and affiliated services

Josh Brown, March 2020.

Summary

ARDC services such as Research Data Australia benefit from the inclusion of PIDs for organisations. These PIDs enable organisations contributing to research outcomes to be identified and linked to research outputs such as data which better enables the tracking of research impact and attribution back to the organisation.

Currently, no organisation ID is used consistently in ARDC services. There are a range of organisation PIDs available, however ROR is the only one that has open, community governance combined with backing from key players (Crossref, Digital Science, DataCite, California Digital Library). As ROR is a relatively new PID (launched January 2019), work is needed to grow adoption among ARDC's partners and to support further development of the ROR.

Background

Organisation identifiers are vital, but frequently overlooked, component of the global research information commons. Recent community consultations highlighted organisations as one of the primary entities the community needed to uniquely identify, alongside people, grants, licenses, data, and publications³⁵.

Much research funding is channelled via organisations. Organisations educate, nurture, and employ research talent. Organisations are the home for research equipment, labs, notebooks, servers, software, repositories and project management. As such, they are a crucial link between all these things, research data, and the people and programs producing them.

Understanding the origin of data, the affiliations of researchers, the location of a data repository, and connecting all these to downstream products and activities are all incredibly important for the health and progress of research. Walking through a few hypotheticals based on the FAIR principles³⁶ shows just how crucial correctly identifying organizations can be:

³⁵ See for example the recent independent advice to the UK government on open access to research, especially annex 6:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/774956/Open-access-to-research-publications-2018.pdf

³⁶ <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

- To **FIND** research data, they must be described correctly, and you need to know where they are housed. Organisations employ data specialists, archivists, and librarians who are trained in creating and curating descriptive metadata.
- Individual researchers are busy, highly mobile people. It is all too often impractical to trace them and send requests for **ACCESS** to data. Organisations act as stewards for much of the data, and have systems and staff in place to safeguard access.
- Ensuring datasets are **INTEROPERABLE** demands the use of standards all the way down. It's not reasonable to expect a critical mass of active researchers to become *au fait* with standards such as RIF-CS³⁷ - instead, organisations offer a crucial pool of expertise and experience in such areas.
- Institutions often control at least part of the Intellectual Property (IP) rights associated with data. For data to be **REUSABLE** we need accurate accounts of which organisations own rights, and how to contact them.

Versions of all these hypotheticals are directly relevant close to home, at the Research Data Australia discovery service for example³⁸, where institutions are the providers of metadata, and the curators of the datasets to which the metadata refer. As such, understanding the current and likely future state of the art in organisation IDs is critical for ARDC.

Landscape overview

A recent joint OCLC and euroCRIS research report analysing evidence of PID usage in research management systems observed that PID “adoption is strongest where the identifier or protocol in question also facilitates interoperability”³⁹. As we have seen, organisation IDs definitely do that, and as a result they have been a major focus of the global research information infrastructure community for several years. Paradoxically, however, the level of adoption for organisation IDs is very low.

In the OCLC/euroCRIS study, 77% of research organisations surveyed used no organisation identifiers. The most adopted PID was the Global Research Identifier Database (GRID) identifier⁴⁰ at 6%, a proportion matched by the aggregated usage of unspecified national identifiers⁴¹. The publishing sector may be the most advanced user of PIDs for organisations, with their adoption of Ringgold identifiers to manage subscriber data⁴².

We are at an early stage, then, in the organisation ID journey, and there is a lot to play for. If we treat PIDs as a foundation for our information systems we need to be aware that the act of

³⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/RIF-CS>

³⁸ <https://researchdata.andis.org.au/>

³⁹ Bryant, R, Clements, A, de Castro, P, Cantrell, J, Dortmund, A, Fansen, J, Gallagher, P, and Mennielli, M. (2018) “Practices and Patterns in Research Information Management: Findings from a Global Survey” Dublin, OH: OCLC Research. Available online at: <https://doi.org/10.25333/BGFG-D241> p80.

⁴⁰ <https://grid.ac/>

⁴¹ Bryant, R *et al*, Op. Cit. p78

⁴² <https://www.ringgold.com/>

building on these foundations creates a significant dependency. It risks placing significant power in the hands of those providing the foundations. The ORCID and DataCite Interoperability Network (ODIN) project explored the challenges of interoperability with and between PID systems, naming ‘trust’ as a necessary element alongside technical interoperability. The “ODIN model introduces the term trusted identifier to refer to digital identifiers which are unique, persistent, descriptive, interoperable and governed.”⁴³ For this reason, we really need to look at the governance and inclusiveness of these infrastructures.

Frankly, the two organisation PIDs mentioned already, GRID and Ringgold, do not meet the requirements to be a trusted PID as they are each controlled by a single, commercial organisation.

The Ringgold identifier is both proprietary and prohibitively expensive, and data, including the identifier itself, cannot be shared with non-subscribing organisations. As such, it is also non-interoperable.

GRID are community-minded, but under the sole control of a company, Digital Science⁴⁴, which is creating products designed to compete with offerings from big corporate entities, such as Elsevier⁴⁵ and Clarivate Analytics⁴⁶. During community discussions about organisation IDs (see below), Digital Science changed the license for GRID data, from CC-BY to CC-0. This was in response to feedback from organisations like ORCID⁴⁷, who pointed out that anything short of fully open licensing harms the reusability of data when it is shared between information infrastructures. On the face of it, this is an excellent development, but it also illustrates the ease with which companies can change their policies. If Digital Science change their model or attitude in future, they could unilaterally impose restrictions on GRID data and the community would have little or no recourse.

This leaves three major international, community-led identifier initiatives which are applicable to research organisations: the Open Funder Registry⁴⁸, the International Standard Name Identifier (ISNI)⁴⁹, and the Research Organisation Registry (ROR)⁵⁰. While all three of these are community-led, they each have weaknesses that need to be considered.

Coverage is a major factor. The specialised Open Funder Registry provides PIDs specifically for funding bodies, and covers ~21,000 organisations. To give a sense of how low that coverage is

⁴³ ODIN Consortium (2013). “Conceptual Model of Interoperability”, p20. Available online at: https://zenodo.org/record/18976/files/D4.1_Conceptual_Model_of_Interoperability.pdf

⁴⁴ <https://www.digital-science.com/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.elsevier.com/en-gb>

⁴⁶ <https://clarivate.com/>

⁴⁷ <https://orcid.org/>

⁴⁸ <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>

⁴⁹ <http://www.isni.org/>

⁵⁰ <https://ror.org/>

in terms of the wider research community, GRID covered 50,000 organisations which had *received* funding at its launch and has grown substantially since then⁵¹.

It makes sense to seek one registry that can cover all the organisational contributors to research, not just funders, or recipients of funding. Thus this review has narrowed the options to two, the reasonably well-established ISNI and the comparatively new ROR.

ROR

The background to the creation of ROR is illuminating. It was essentially created as a corrective to the perceived shortcomings of existing organisation IDs. Crossref⁵², DataCite⁵³ and ORCID held a workshop to discuss the nature and extent of gaps in organisation identifier provision in April 2016, and prepared a number of analyses to support this work⁵⁴. In November 2016, they announced a project to address the concerns they had identified⁵⁵, followed with a lively debate at PIDapalooza⁵⁶ 2016 in Reykjavik.

Throughout 2017, a community group⁵⁷ met and evaluated incumbent organisation identifier providers (including ISNI), issuing a request for information⁵⁸ late in the year to seek input from those providers as to how they intended to address the needs of the scholarly community. In January 2018, a community meeting⁵⁹ was held in Girona, co-located with the second PIDapalooza, to hear more from the respondents and to discuss options.

As a result of this process, ROR was launched in January 2019. It drew on data from the GRID database, covering ~90,000 organisations from the global research community. It is focused on “proper description of relationships between contributors, contributions, research sponsors, publishers, and employers”⁶⁰. It has an API for access to data. Its development was overseen by a joint committee comprising representatives from California Digital Library (CDL), Crossref, DataCite, and Digital Science. ROR was developed and launched with seed funding from Crossref, donated data from Digital Science, and technical and management support from CDL and DataCite.

⁵¹ <https://www.digital-science.com/blog/news/digital-science-launches-grid-a-new-global-open-database-offering-unique-information-on-research-organisations/>

⁵² <https://www.crossref.org/>

⁵³ <https://datacite.org/>

⁵⁴ See: Organization Identifier Provider Landscape (Bilder, Brown, & Demeranville, 2016), <https://doi.org/10.5438/4716> and Technical Considerations for an Organization Identifier Registry (Fenner, Paglione, Demeranville, & Bilder, 2016), <https://doi.org/10.5438/7885>

⁵⁵ <https://blog.datacite.org/announcing-organization-identifier-project/#ref=https://doi.org/10.5438/4716>

⁵⁶ <https://www.pidapalooza.org/>

⁵⁷ <https://orcid.org/content/organization-identifier-working-group>

⁵⁸ Laurel, Haak; Pentz, Edward; Cruse, Patricia; Chodacki, John (2017): Organization Identifier Project: Request for Information. figshare. Journal contribution. <https://doi.org/10.23640/07243.5458162.v1>

⁵⁹ <https://orcid.org/content/2018-org-id-meeting>

⁶⁰ <https://ror.org/scope/>

ROR does not have a business model. It has a newly launched community steering group⁶¹. It has launched as a 'Minimum Viable Product', and is currently developing new features, including tools to support record self-management by organisations. It maps to other organisation IDs. The data is fully open.

ISNI

ISNI emerged from the library community and consists of a global database of named entities. This includes organisations as well as people, companies and fictional characters. It ingests PIDs from other systems to enrich its metadata and to help with disambiguation. There are a range of ISNI Registration Agencies (RAs), and most of the updates to ISNI records are managed by 'quality teams' at the British Library⁶² and the Bibliothèque nationale de France⁶³. Much of ISNI's governance comes from communities outside research, and it is not primarily intended to serve the research community. Much of its usage comes from rights management and the content industry. It does not have a reliable, scalable API.

The Ringgold company, which serves as an ISNI RA and holds a seat on the ISNI board, built an API service called 'Open ISNI for Organizations'⁶⁴. This offers programmatic access to details of around 400,000 organisations. The drawback of this arrangement is that the API is provided on a goodwill basis by a corporate entity. It is undoubtedly a generous act, and the effort it took should not be underestimated. However, the service needs to be placed on a sustainable footing before it can be adopted by the community. At the moment, a change of management or financial priority at Ringgold could result in the disappearance of the resource.

ISNI itself has no dedicated technical resource to build or maintain services, relying on OCLC to provide a supporting infrastructure. Progress and changes to ISNI systems have historically been very slow. ISNI published a blog post in August 2017, in response to the research community demands expressed in the precursor to the ROR project in which they announced a number of enhancements to the way ISNI would collect, correct and share data about organisations⁶⁵. At the time of writing, there have been no further updates on this project since that post was published⁶⁶ and none of the promised improvements have been delivered.

Neither ISNI nor ROR is currently perfect, and each comes with uncertainties. ISNI has issues with responsiveness, focus and reliability. ROR has issues around sustainability and future governance.

⁶¹ <https://ror.org/blog/2019-11-22-meet-the-ror-steering-group/>

⁶² <https://www.bl.uk/>

⁶³ <https://www.bnf.fr/en>

⁶⁴ <https://isni.ringgold.com/>

⁶⁵ <http://www.isni.org/content/isni-organizations-registry-identifying-organizations-scholarly-supply-chain>

⁶⁶ <http://www.isni.org/news>

Considerations

The issue of PIDs for organisations has come to a head, as ROR is currently appealing for sponsors to provide donations in support of its running costs. ARDC has been approached directly, and asked to contribute. Their goal is to raise US\$175,000 over the next two years. ROR currently has no other way to raise funds.

The ROR partnership overlaps significantly with ARDC's global network of peers and collaborators. ROR is heavily involved with, and supported by, the Freya project⁶⁷, which includes ARDC as an unfunded partner. DataCite are providing significant support and participate on the steering committee. ARDC sits on the DataCite board. Crossref provided the initial investment in ROR and are partnering with ARDC on several projects, including Freya and pilots for grant identifiers. Strategically, an investment (either financial or in-kind) seems like a very small price to pay to remain at the top table of the global research data and PID communities. If nothing else, it would send a very strong message that ARDC was a partner to be relied upon.

As noted above, ARDC needs organisation IDs. At the moment, provision in this space is uneven, unreliable, and unpredictable. This needs to improve, and urgently. Questions to be considered in throwing support behind one scheme or another include: who can ARDC influence most? Which of these initiatives is likely to be most responsive to ARDC members and services' needs? Via which initiative will ARDC be able to deliver the greatest benefit to the Australian research community? Given the people and organisations involved, and the relative youth and scale of the operation, ROR seems like the likeliest candidate by far.

Another factor to consider is which has the greatest chance of 'persisting'? The service, parent organisation, and data all need to be available and reliable long term. As a start-up, ROR loses out to ISNI on this criterion, as ISNI is backed by a large, global, diversified network of sustainable organisations. That said, their will to invest in ISNI is clearly minimal. It may be easier to assure the persistence of the smaller ROR with investment and support than to rely on a limited, under-resourced but currently more nominally 'persistable' incumbent.

Finally, ARDC should look at the use cases for organisation IDs. Which initiative offers the closest match to the needs of ARDC given that the primary need is to ensure that its partners, collaborators and contributors are unambiguously identified within and across research data services? ROR's mission states that "ROR is intended for use by the research community, for the purposes of increasing the use of organization identifiers in the community and enabling connections between organization records in various systems. Implementation of ROR IDs in scholarly infrastructure and metadata will enable more efficient discovery and tracking of research outputs across institutions and funding bodies."⁶⁸ This is a pretty good *prima facie* match for ARDC's needs.

⁶⁷ <https://www.project-freya.eu/en>

⁶⁸ <https://ror.org/about/>

Recommendations

On balance, it seems that the smaller organisation dedicated exclusively to the research community and offering the greatest chance of direct engagement would be a better bet at this stage, since shifting practice and thinking at the larger incumbent has proved difficult.

Currently, no organisation ID is used consistently in ARDC services. The RIF-CS schema includes GRID as an identifier type, but GRID IDs are scarcely if at all used by contributors to Research Data Australia. GRID IDs are simply shown as a resolvable link to the GRID information page for the organisation to which they refer, if they are present in records. The current plan is to implement new functionality in Research Data Australia which will allow vocabulary publishers to search for and link to organisation identifiers when describing the vocabulary. The proposal is to use the ROR API to deliver this functionality.

This planned enhancement to Research Data Australia offers a chance to promote organisation IDs to the community. If other services can be encouraged to use ROR IDs, that could bootstrap coverage in metadata records, and motivate adoption nationally. A one-off project could create a good level of coverage for historical records, boosting the consistency and predictability of identifier coverage, and maximising the benefits for users and organisations.

That said, it makes sense to integrate more than one organisation ID. While this could be seen as extra overhead, we should note that while there is a major need for organisation PIDs for the academic research sector, and this sector has some very specific needs that must shape such a system, it cannot be the only identifier used for organisations. Non-academic organisations are involved in data creation, and researchers will move between academia and industry. To capture those relationships, systems will need to support other IDs, like the Australian Business Number (ABN)⁶⁹. In light of this, the pragmatic approach is to take advantage of richer features and dedicated coverage for research organisations while maintaining the capacity to support the widest possible range of identifiers to cover Australian businesses, international organisations and the like.

In short, ARDC already plans to implement ROR, ROR seems like the best, most trustworthy match for ARDC's needs, and ARDC has a chance to boost adoption of ROR IDs, while remaining open to any other organisation IDs that may be appropriate for those outside the core research community.

In light of this, **ARDC should be willing to invest in ROR**. There are four ways this could be done:

- 1) One-off contribution or recurring project funding for ROR.
- 2) Providing development or other practical resources to ROR to accelerate the creation of value-add services that will help it to become sustainable.

⁶⁹ <https://abr.business.gov.au/>

- 3) Implementing ROR IDs in ARDC services, and providing practical support and strong encouragement to the Australian research community to start using them.
- 4) Establish a benefits realisation program, to track metrics and develop case studies which can be used to communicate the value of ROR to the Australian community.

The third option is already implied by the roadmap for Research Data Australia. However, for this to deliver long-term results, ARDC will need to throw a little more weight behind ROR to accelerate enhancements to the service and to ensure that it is around for the long haul. Any of the strategic, practical, political or community benefits on their own would be convincing. Taken altogether, it would seem unwise not to find some way to support ROR at this critical phase in its evolution.

Appendix 4: Grant/investment IDs

Josh Brown and Natasha Simons, March 2020

Introduction

Grant numbers have long been used as an administrative tool to track awards, contracts and associated activities. Within funder systems, or in an institutional research management system, any number can function as a serial number. For this reason, many funders have used a plain six digit number to identify their grants. Unfortunately, when research reaches internet scale, such an approach quickly falls apart. Searching Europe PMC for grant number 207467 returns results for grants from Wellcome Trust and the European Research Council, both of which have the same grant reference number.

The value of a unique grant reference is neatly demonstrated in a case study published on the ORCID blog.⁷⁰ A unique grant number, published with a description of the grant and the primary investigator's ORCID iD on UKRI's 'Gateway to Research' database can be subsequently linked to outputs via the ORCID registry, and then to Europe PMC, where other associated grants, researchers, and outputs can all be linked to the original grant. These connections are vital to understanding hitherto undiscoverable connections and impacts which have resulted from research support, but making and exposing these connections is often labour intensive and error prone.

As Robert Kiley and Nina Frentrop of the Wellcome Trust observed in 2018, "Currently, researchers are typically asked to manually disclose what outputs have arisen from their funding. In the future, such disclosures would be fully automated. If a global ID system for grants was developed, publishers and repositories could require these to be disclosed on submission, and this data could then programmatically be passed to researcher assessment platforms."⁷¹

Automating such connections could offer measurable benefits in a range of known problem areas. For instance, funders often cannot reliably monitor the impact of shared research facilities. It's hard to track which researchers have used those facilities, and see what publications, projects and future collaborations have emerged as a result of their investment. Funding supports studentships, and provides training and career development opportunities, but we struggle to understand the career patterns and pathways of funded researchers as they move onwards through academia and industry. Finally, we need to simplify the process of opening up access to research. It's surprisingly difficult for researchers to show that they have complied with funder policies for outputs, whether for FAIR data or Open Access.

⁷⁰ <https://orcid.org/blog/2019/03/14/connected-research>

⁷¹ <https://www.crossref.org/blog/wellcome-explains-the-benefits-of-developing-an-open-and-global-grant-identifier/>

Persistent identifiers have proven their worth in exposing connections across the global research network. Given the fundamental enabling role that funding support plays in this network, it is surely time that more, and better, data about funding was embedded into research management, content creation and discovery systems. Identifiers for grants offer a way to achieve this.

The state of the art:

Internationally, the most advanced use of grant metadata is in linking funding to subsequent outputs, especially publications. However, everything we know about the state of the art in this endeavour shows serious problems. A recent survey by ORCID found that “the primary challenge reported by funders is connecting grants to subsequent research activities and outputs”⁷² ORCID’s report goes on to state that “While most funders state that the majority of their reporting requests are fulfilled, much of the information reported is provided late or of low quality and requires time-consuming clean-up.”

Many publisher-facilitated funding acknowledgements use Open Funder Registry identifiers. These link to the organisation providing the funding, rather than the specific grant. Given that this initiative has been in wide use since 2012 and covers more than 21,000 funders, one could reasonably expect a reasonable level of connections between those organisations and outputs they have supported. However, Crossref funding search shows that of ~112M outputs registered with them, only ~4.6M have funding data associated with them.⁷³ Of that 4.6M, Crossref report that only around half use a unique funder ID. Clearly, a lot of funding acknowledgements are getting lost on their way through publisher systems.

Grant IDs to track ARDC investment

ARDC is seeking to use a grant identifier to identify ARDC investment. The grant identifier is distinct from a RAID identifier, the latter of which would be used to identify project activities and act like a container for many identifiers (people, organizations, grants, outputs, facilities).

Having an ARDC grant/investment identifier will ensure that ARDC’s investment contribution is clearly identifiable within a project that may have multiple investors. It is not unusual for impactful projects to have multiple investment sources - see this example from NHRMC⁷⁴.

Another specific use for a grant/investment id is to give funded projects a clear way to attribute ARDC’s involvement in their project. The European Commission, for example, requires this statement on project websites: "OpenAIRE-Advance receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 777541." Such a statement with a globally unique grant ID would be significantly more helpful in tracking outcomes.

⁷² <https://doi.org/10.23640/07243.9149240.v1>

⁷³ <https://search.crossref.org/funding>

⁷⁴ <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/resources/fetal-alcohol-spectrum-disorder-public-health-case-study>

Grant identifiers for Australian research funders

ARDC has been providing 'Persistent URLs' (PURLs) for Australian grants since 2009. RDA shows ~16.5k ARC grants with a PURL, ~32.3k NHMRC grants with a PURL and 90 Department of the environment grants with a PURL. While the data is available via the RDA API, the number of organisations consuming the data is not currently known. ARDC staff report that Griffith University were using the API to link outputs to grant data, but that was some time ago and the current status of that activity is not known. PURLs do not appear to be widely used in funding acknowledgements. A random sample of 15 grant searches in Google Scholar returned no results for any of the PURLs, whereas the corresponding grant number (usually the final 9 characters of the PURL) did return papers.

Global initiative to better track the impact of grants through identifiers

In 2019, Crossref launched a new service, providing DOIs for grants. The aim of this service is to create a global registry of grants, with descriptive information including PIDs for investigators, organisations, projects and connected grants. Crossref are building 'search and lookup' tools which will be built into publisher and repository systems to enable those submitting content to repositories to link the grant ID and associated information (such as canonical acknowledgement text, content curation or access policies etc.) to be imported into the platform alongside their content.

The vision of this system is that links between funding and outputs will be made visible and accurate, and the resulting connections between PIDs (say, a DataCite DOI, and ORCID iD and a grant ID) could act as triggers to automate processes. Crossref and ORCID already have a live example of just such a process in the 'ORCID auto-update' mechanism. Briefly, an author submits an article and adds their ORCID iD to the submission. The publisher registers a DOI for the article, and includes the author's ORCID iD in the metadata they send to Crossref as part of that process. Crossref detects the ORCID iD and sends the article metadata to the authors ORCID record, from where it can propagate to repositories, funder reporting systems and so on. This creates close to real-time updates on output publication for any organisation working with the author.

There are solid grounds for optimism that this vision can be delivered. Crossref metadata APIs already deliver data to most major repository platforms. More than 12,000 publishers around the world have joined Crossref to register DOIs for content. DOIs are widely used, and are well understood by system vendors and developers. The level of interest from funders is extremely promising. There are pilots under way to explore the ways that grant metadata could be enhanced to tackle specific issues, such as making content policies machine actionable.

ARDC is working with Crossref on a related initiative, to expand the grant metadata schema to better capture infrastructure grants (i.e. a grant consisting in the provision of, or access to, a

research enabling infrastructure) in partnership with the US Department of Energy, The UK's Science and Technology Facilities Council, and the Dutch national funder.

These developments are designed to plug directly into existing international infrastructures (such as ORCID IDs) and to operate at an international scale. This makes sense, as research is itself international, as is most publishing activity. Pragmatically, there is a much greater chance of getting actors to integrate a small number of international, potentially multi-purpose identifier systems than there is of successfully persuading them to integrate multiple, incompatible, bespoke national systems.

Proposal:

The drivers for the ARDC to assign DOIs for grants using Crossref are:

1. To identify, link and track research infrastructure investments
2. To adhere to international best practice i.e. assigning Crossref DOIs as grant identifiers

It will also provide an opportunity to demonstrate to Australian research funders currently using the PURL service what international best practice is. The cost of maintaining the current PURL system is very small. Staff report spending as little as an hour a year adding domains and updating the system. Any change to the status quo should be based on a solid business case and a balanced assessment of the costs and potential benefits.

The first step for assigning grant IDs to investments is for **ARDC to join Crossref**. Based on Crossref's membership and fee structure⁷⁵, the costs would be US\$600 per year for membership with a charge of US\$2 per DOI registered⁷⁶. The membership fee is based on the annual value of grants awarded. In this case ARDC sits in the tier based on annual awards worth between US\$2.1M and US\$10M. The maximum annual membership fee for grant IDs is capped at US\$1,200.

The second step is to **assign DOIs to ARDC investments**. Advice from Crossref received by ARDC on 28 February 2020 is that at the moment, the only way for funders to register research grants with Crossref is to send XML files. They are planning to extend their API to support registration of and searching for grants in 2020. There isn't a manual deposit form (like DataCite's Fabrica) yet, but again, they're planning to integrate more manual registration of grant IDs into various content registration tools in future. This means that the process of assigning grant identifiers to ARDC investments is technically and administratively extremely low barrier (a single XML file will do it) and low cost.

Grant DOI linking and discovery tools should be built into ARDC services, such as Research Data Australia. In this way, grantees can be supported in demonstrating impact, and

⁷⁵ <https://www.crossref.org/services/content-registration/grants/#membership-fees>

⁷⁶ <https://www.crossref.org/fees/#annual-membership-fees-funders>

the scale and nature of ARDC's investment results will be made easier to track. This tracking will enable **ARDC to conduct a quantitative and qualitative assessment of the benefits of grant ID-enabled connections**, both in terms of data coverage and new reporting and analysis possibilities.

As new good practices emerge around identifying and tracking grants emerge, ARDC should be well placed to evaluate and recommend these practices for the Australian community.

Appendix 5: Identifiers for instruments

Josh Brown, March 2020

Introduction

The importance of scientific instruments in the production of research data has come to the fore in recent years. The instruments that are used to collect and process raw data represent a significant investment and resource base for research, and also have a fundamental relationship with the data they generate.

Key ARDC partners, such as the National Imaging Facility (NIF) and the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO) manage a huge range of instruments, for example. These instruments are not only vital to the performance of their respective missions, they are integral to the interoperability and reusability of data. Understanding a dataset requires some understanding of the means of its production. The instruments, software versions and other determinants provide crucial context for those seeking to understand the nature, scope and potential limitations of a dataset. In the quest for more reproducible research, tracking instruments and related outputs is required.

Internationally, the Research Data Alliance has hosted a working group on the Persistent Identification of Instruments⁷⁷. ARDC staff have contributed to this group, as have AARNet, CSIRO, and Australian research organisations. This group has created a schema for the description of instruments, which can be used to structure the necessary metadata associated with an instrument PID. In the Australian context, PIDs for instruments have emerged as an area of significant interest, in part as a result of the high level of engagement with global efforts in this area. This has led to the establishment of a national PIDs for instruments Community of Practice, facilitated by ARDC.

So far, the NIF have been the most active in implementing instrument PIDs. They have begun using the ARDC Handle service to register Handles for their instrument base, and creating their own metadata using the Research Data Alliance schema. The Handle and metadata are exposed via Research Data Australia, with the Handle itself resolving to a landing page in the NIF database.

Internationally, DataCite are extending their schema to include instruments, meaning that they can provide a central discovery service with DOIs for instruments and easier integration with value-add services such as Scholix and Event Data. A recent blog post sets out their plans and reiterates the importance of instruments to the understanding of data: “The capacity to uniquely identify an instrument is critical for the community to gather contextual information and interpret the related data accordingly.”⁷⁸

⁷⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/persistent-identification-instruments-wg>

⁷⁸ <https://blog.datacite.org/pids-for-instruments-a-way-forward/>

Considerations

The NIF implementation indicates that the Research Data Alliance schema is fit for purpose. As it updates and expands over time, they will need to maintain their own repository to reflect the evolution of best practice. With the need for development work to implement the PID registration process and to create landing pages for instruments in local repositories, this approach might only be accessible to larger organisations or those with the largest stable of instruments.

At a national scale, the effort and resources involved in equipping every Australian organisation that could benefit from instrument PIDs could be non-trivial in the short term. Competing priorities and varying levels of expertise will mean that roll out will be slow, and adoption uneven. Practically speaking, implementing the new schema across the whole network will take time. The implementation will need to be converted into product specifications, added to the roadmaps of several repository platforms, coded, and either implemented by service providers or by local teams. Local implementation implies another cycle of prioritisation and road mapping, adding another layer of unpredictability and potential delay. Scaling this up to achieve consistent coverage will be a real challenge.

That said, the value of this endeavour will be highest when coverage is most complete. Predictable and reliable information about instruments will encourage the use of that information, helping (for instance) organisations funding or providing access to instruments to understand their impact. In addition, a complete picture of instrument use and availability will help to support better targeting of investments and enable the re-use or sharing of instruments in some cases, potentially saving money and speeding up research.

The cost of providing PIDs for instruments is tiny compared to the cost of providing the instruments themselves. That said, it may prove a challenge to assure consistent buy-in across the sector. As the Australian DataCite model (in all probability) moves to member organisations paying fees for DOIs, DataCite is bringing in per-DOI charging or increased fees per tier, alongside per-repository fees, which will increase the cost of using their services.

It is hard to predict what the costs will pan out to be if each organisation pays for their own DOI registrations, as instruments are numerous and unevenly distributed. The risk is that adding a per-DOI charge for thousands of instruments on top of the costs of obtaining DOIs for data etc. could create sticker shock and cause attrition to consortium membership.

What can be predicted is that start-up costs will be higher than ongoing costs. Many organisations have a current crop of instruments which last for multiple years, and have spent years assembling that collection. The initial costs of registering current instruments will be high with a lower 'maintenance' state to follow when only new instruments are to be added as they come online. An approach that smooths out that initial 'bump' will be vital to ensure participation at the stage when benefits are a vision. Over time, as evidence mounts, maintaining engagement should become easier.

The strategic principle '**partnership is leadership**' is particularly applicable here. Even the first mover in this space, NIF, is operating using the schema collaboratively developed by the

Research Data Alliance working group. Continued collaboration will be the key to implementing and developing the schema in future. This will help to optimise the return on investment for the sector. Ensuring that the PIDs for instruments community of practice inputs into the work will also help to foster buy-in within the wider Australian community.

The second major guiding principle is that '**research is global**'. The schema developed as part of an international effort, and is being implemented in global systems. If this can be pushed out to the Australian community using international tools and systems that they already use, it would reduce friction and consolidate effort.

Finally, the third principle is '**pick your battles**'. ARDC is already heavily involved with this work, and with data repositories, and with data aggregation services. ARDC has already acknowledged the importance of instrument PIDs, has already invested time and effort in them, and is well placed to drive their adoption.

The goal should be to **maximise the coverage of instrument PIDs, while minimising cost, and friction**. There is a need to shorten the runway to adoption as far as possible and, in the interest of both coverage and equity, make sure that all partner institutions have a way to access and obtain instrument PIDs.

Proposal:

ARDC should build a central instrument portal in Research Data Australia, which registers instruments with DataCite, provides a simple metadata record with an (optional) landing page, and mints a DOI for each. Those with the most need or capacity can provide local landing pages if they wish, and ARDC could support any institutions who wish to extend their local repository to include instruments over time. While this intervention is the planning phase, **ARDC should work with both the Persistent Identification of Instruments Working Group and DataCite's Metadata Working Group** to shape and track the evolution of the schema to ensure that ARDC's members and partners are ready to benefit at the earliest possible moment.

Rationale:

This approach contains costs.

The impact on the consortium cost of more than a very few repositories adding instruments alongside content could be significantly more expensive. For example, under the proposed DOI fee option A just three repositories registering enough instruments each year to move them from the 101-500 band to the 501-1,000 band would add €1,500 to the consortium fee, enough to register 10,000 DOIs at a single repository. The result is that fees for instrument DOIs for the whole Australian community could be capped at €3,850 under option A, or €3,750 under option B. (See Appendix 2, above.)

As noted above, registering and obtaining PIDs for a full back inventory could be expensive for a single organisation. Scaled that up across multiple organisations, costs could be very high. Providing a single registration service and linking it into RDA will smooth out the cost profile and

enable organisations to quantify any benefits before moving forward with their own local arrangements.

A central instrument PID portal lowers the burden on the sector.

Building one dedicated portal which any research-performing organisation can access and add instruments to will concentrate expertise, meaning ARDC can provide better support services at scale for the initiative, and means that 50-60 repositories do not need to make potentially major modifications.

This approach brings time to consistent deployment right down.

Since there will be no need to specify how multiple platforms should interact with instrument metadata/DOIs and then wait for the project to work its way through the roadmaps of dozens of institutions with competing priorities and variable expertise, this approach vastly shortens the path to consistent adoption and benefits realisation.

ARDC expertise can improve the maintainability of the schema and local services.

Setting up the portal and supporting the community in working with instrument PIDs in the way that works best for them provides ARDC with an advocacy role to help to keep the Research Data Alliance work moving. This means that schema updates etc. can be managed in a more timely manner, and the evolving needs of the Australian research sector will be served by ARDC's global voice.

Appendix 6: Handle services review

Josh Brown, April 2020

Introduction

Handles emerged in the early 1990s as a means of providing a fixed reference for digital entities. The global Handle system is overseen by the not-for-profit DONA foundation⁷⁹, based in Geneva. Handles underpin a number of systems. For example, it is worth noting that DOIs are a type of Handle, but others also exist. DOI Registration Agencies like Crossref and DataCite participate in governance of the Handle system, as well as having their own, community-specific governance. Other notable providers of Handles include the European Persistent Identifier Consortium (ePIC)⁸⁰, membership of which is open to national IT centres.

Handles provide a lightweight and flexible identifier system. They can be used as the foundation for full-featured and complex networks of services, like DataCite, or as a minimal system to enable reliable links to resources. They are widely used in the research space - for example, ePIC focuses on research objects, and the DSpace repository platform creates Handles for all the digital objects contained within a DSpace instance. As such, they have been a natural fit for ARDC's evolving service portfolio, both due to their widespread use in the Australian community and thanks to their potential to be used as a foundational component of data services.

As a low-cost and relatively simple system, Handles have been used to provide persistence to emergent ARDC services, such as RAiD. The ability to build innovative services without the burden of adaptation to a pre-existing major service architecture provides ARDC with an experimental platform and consequently a strategic advantage in an evolving research data landscape, in line with the goal to provide leading edge e-infrastructure.

That said, the use of any PID brings with it the promise to persist, and therefore this review focuses on the persistability of ARDC Handle-based services. In their current form, they raise a number of issues which should be relatively straightforward to address. If, however, they are not addressed, then they could develop into unacceptable risks to ARDC's core goals in providing FAIR data services.

The state of the art

The Handle at ARDC was launched in 2009, and has minted more than 80,000 Handles since then. The technical infrastructure for the service is hosted by the Australian National University and does not represent a cost to ARDC. The support and development time used to maintain the service are reported as averaging out at 0.2 EFT. The service has absorbed very little development effort in more than 10 years.

⁷⁹ <https://www.dona.net/index>

⁸⁰ <https://www.pidconsortium.net/>

As the volume of Handles has grown, the need for some kind of redundancy and backup has come to the fore. ARDC team members have had preliminary conversations with ePIC, to investigate the possibility of joining their consortium. ePIC provides access to Handle registration services, and a guaranteed range of Handle prefixes, but the key value proposition for ARDC of membership lies in the reciprocal arrangements between ePIC members in providing redundancy for the resolution and identifier services. In essence, ARDC would continue to maintain its own Local Handle Server (LHS) and would agree to mirror the LHSs of a number of other ePIC members. In return, the consortium members will provide reciprocal mirroring for ARDC. This means that if the ARDC service experiences downtime for any reason, the Handle links will still resolve to the data repository (or other digital resource) to which the Handle refers.

The cost of ePIC membership would be €7,500 (~AUD 12,900 at the time of writing) per year. It is possible to migrate the existing ARDC Handle service into the ePIC system, so existing commitments to persistence would be honoured. The consensus among ARDC staff is that the reciprocal mirroring could be offered at minimal cost, as it is purely the Handle servers which are replicated. Metadata and content would still be housed elsewhere, meaning storage costs and bandwidth should be contained.

Within ARDC, the RAiD service currently uses Handles as the underpinning PIDs for its Data Management Records (DMRs). RAiD usage just within Australia is likely to increase significantly over the coming years, and international interest in the service is strong. Together, this is likely to require service level guarantees for RAiDs to resolve consistently, and ePIC could provide a vital redundancy layer to support ARDC in meeting those requirements.

The ARDC LHS is also the 'resolver of last resort' for Australian universities. Several institutions have changed their repository platform and as a result have closed down their own LHS, which once supported their repository content. ARDC has picked up those Handles and keeps the PIDs which used to be served by the repository alive. These 'orphan Handles' are, sadly, a fact of life and their number is also likely to grow.

Considerations for ARDC

The flexibility afforded by Handle enables ARDC to build services that are tailored to the needs of Australian research, and to work with international partners to innovate and extend those services. Handles are a critical dependency for other ARDC services. ARDC provides a 'final home' for orphaned Handles, and to pull back from this would be a blow to the credibility of ARDC as a 'safe pair of hands' for data, and for the persistence of identifiers. Taken together, these considerations make a good case for the continuation of Handle services at ARDC.

That said, the current situation is not sustainable, and poses unnecessary risks to downstream services and to the Findability of data and resources. The current system relies on resources provided by ARDC partners, like ANU. Reliance on donated infrastructure is a great way to keep

costs down, but as services grow, the risk rises that it will become too costly or complex to continue on a 'goodwill' basis.

ePIC membership has the potential to be a valuable step towards a more formalised and robust Handle offering. However, it should be noted that it offers only a partial solution and comes with overhead. The costs associated with mirroring other LHSs should be low, but are hard to predict with certainty. Costs should also be considered in the context of the reputational damage that would ensue if an ARDC service were to fail, and the benefits that could come from stronger international infrastructure partnerships.

RAiD and Handle could also be a mutually reinforcing pair of services. The systems are already coupled, and it could be possible to rationalise costs by coupling them more tightly. RAiD income may also help to offset the costs of maintaining the LHS and ePIC membership.

The critical gap which would not be filled by ePIC is metadata. ePIC only backs up the Handle, the URL to which it refers and descriptions associated with the Handle itself. It does not provide redundancy or back up for the metadata which is critical to the resources identified, and the basis for value-add services built upon the PID system. There will need to be a scalable infrastructure to maintain service level access, uptime, and redundancy for metadata in addition to resolution backup.

Recommendations

Once again, the strategic principle that **Partnership is leadership** is central to this review. Working with ePIC and others will extend and enhance ARDC's global collaboration network.

The second major principle in play here is that **data is at risk**. ARDC must address this by building resilience into the service portfolio, and encouraging the sector to plan for the long term accessibility of data and resources.

Transitioning away from Handle would incur ongoing costs and could result in a loss of operational flexibility, depending on any constraints of the replacement system. It also risks disruption to services or loss of data in the transition process. Handles are established in global good practice for PIDs for data and other research outputs and entities, and are embedded as a dependency in the ARDC data and services portfolio (and underpin emerging potentially very high-impact services such as RAiD). In light of this, **ARDC should continue to provide Handle services**. In so doing, there needs to be a process of 'professionalising' ARDC's Handle services, to reduce risks to the operation to safeguard both data and ARDC's reputation. Therefore, **ARDC should join ePIC to assure the continuity of Handle resolution and minting services**.

To extend that assurance to the metadata and software stacks that underpin ARDC's Handle-based services, **ARDC should transition away from the reliance on donated infrastructure**,

and transition to an enterprise solution for primary service provision and use Australian partners as additional local backup at most.

When the final responses to this review have been agreed and the shape of the ARDC PID portfolio has been agreed, the **Data and Services team should explore ways that Handle-based services could be coupled to rationalise costs.**

Finally, the **Data and Services team should investigate the level and sophistication of Handle adoption across the sector and plan for the need to transition institutional LHSs in-house as bulk transfers.** By assuring persistent, reliable, and consistent services for Australian researchers, ARDC can bolster the integrity of the research system.

Appendix 7: ORCID support review

Josh Brown, March 2020

Introduction

The Open Researcher and Contributor Identifier (ORCID) was launched in 2012 to solve the name ambiguity problem in scholarly communications. Put simply, researchers get credit for their work by linking their name to it, just as an artist signs a painting. Unfortunately, names are not unique (more than 40% of Korean researchers share the family name Kim for example) which means works can be easily misattributed. The scale of modern research demands a better way to link people to their works, activities, funding and all the other myriad contributions an individual might make to the advancement of human knowledge.

Given that a person is a relatively stable entity, the use of persistent identifiers for people is an obvious solution to this problem. The identifier can act as a digital name, guaranteed to be unique, and can be readily associated with outputs, such as data or software, as well as inputs such as grant applications or infrastructure access.

While other identifiers had tried to fill this gap, some were proprietary and designed to privilege a particular corporate product ecosystem (such as the Scopus Author ID⁸¹ or Research ID⁸²), or were not designed with integration in research workflows in mind (such as the International Standard Name Identifier⁸³). ORCID, as an open alternative (using open data and open source software) designed for and run by the research community, was adopted quickly around the world and, according to research by euroCRIS and OCLC, has emerged as a de facto standard person identifier in research management systems⁸⁴.

Australia was also swift to spot the potential of ORCID, and to coordinate a national approach, as exemplified by ANDS work with the Australasian Research Management Society, the Council of Australian University Librarians and Universities Australia to agree and issue a joint statement of principle in support of ORCID in April 2015⁸⁵. Australia's major funders simultaneously released a joint statement encouraging all researchers applying for funding to have an ORCID iD⁸⁶. This was followed by the launch of a national ORCID consortium, managed and supported by the Australian Access Federation in February 2016.

ANDS and subsequently ARDC played a critical role in the development and governance of the consortium, in recognition of the needs of infrastructure providers to integrate PIDs consistently and reliably across the services that researchers and their home institutions use. The level of

⁸¹ <https://www.scopus.com/freelookup/form/author.uri>

⁸² <https://www.researcherid.com/#rid-for-researchers>

⁸³ <http://www.isni.org/>

⁸⁴ <https://doi.org/10.25333/BGFG-D241>

⁸⁵ http://ands.org.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0007/417346/orcid-joint-statement-of-principle.pdf

⁸⁶ <https://www.arc.gov.au/news-publications/media/communiques/communique-4-may-2015>

buy-in, engagement and community support for the consortium testifies eloquently to ORCID's importance to Australian, and international, research.

The state of the art

The Australian ORCID consortium has 42 members at the time of writing. 33 of those members have integrated the ORCID API into one or more of their systems, for a total of 39 live integrations. Many of these are custom integrations with local systems, so it is difficult to make assumptions about precisely what functionality they offer. The next largest groups of integrations are with commercial platforms (11 have linked ORCID to their Symplectic Elements research management system, and 8 have integrated with Elsevier's Pure research management system). Finally, there are several integrations with open source platforms such as EPrints or VIVO.

Of the non-institutional integrations, there are several which are of the highest general visibility and value to Australian researchers.

Both DataCite and Crossref have developed an 'auto-update' system. Put simply, when either of those organisations detects an ORCID iD linked to a DOI registered with them, they ask permission to update the associated ORCID record, and then push metadata about that, and subsequent, outputs to the ORCID registry. From there, it can be sent to institutions, funders and other organisations which might have an interest in that researcher's work.

The next exemplar integration is well-placed to benefit from the presence of that data. ARC's grant management can draw in data from the ORCID record of any funding applicant and use this data to pre-populate basic factual information in a grant application. The researcher (and former ORCID board member) Richard de Grijis wrote in a blog post of how he had seen ORCID as something that was primarily useful for research administrators until he discovered the ARC integration:

"...my indifference changed to excitement when I applied for my first research grant using the Australian Research Council's web-based research management system at the beginning of this year.

The ARC had introduced a new feature that made my life as a grant applicant much simpler: instead of manually copying and pasting my bibliography into the relevant boxes, I could now pull my research outputs directly into the system by linking to the ORCID repository. Needless to say, this development saved me—and many other researchers nationwide—a significant amount of time"⁸⁷

There is also an emerging role for ORCID in ARDC services. ORCID has a potentially rich relationship with the Research Activity Identifier (RAiD). Currently, administrator access to RAiD

⁸⁷ <https://orcid.org/blog/2019/11/04/time-flies>

records is managed using AAF sign-in, but for international collaborators on RAiD records, ORCID's single sign-in solution could eliminate a barrier to adoption and interaction with the service. Also, on a metadata level, ORCID can be used to link both people and their works to RAiD records. Internationally, the European 'Knowledge Exchange' group⁸⁸ is developing a RAiD-based portfolio called the Openness Profile, the model for which relies on ORCID and RAiD identifiers and metadata.

That said, ORCID has limits. It is dependent on researchers obtaining iDs and populating their ORCID records. Solutions like Auto-Update rely on researchers granting systems permission to interact with their ORCID records. Neither of these things happen in the absence of awareness and understanding of what ORCID is, and how it can help researchers. It is telling that Richard de Grijis was a member of the ORCID board for two years and it was only in the last few months of that time that he saw real-life benefit from his ORCID iD.

For ORCID to deliver on its potential, both for researchers and for ARDC services, it needs to be ubiquitous, understood, and used. Work like that undertaken by ARC will go a long way to help with this, but it remains a major challenge to assess ORCID adoption, let alone researchers' understanding of it. AAF are doing work in this space with the ORCID consortium and they have developed a Maturity Model which will provide data on the levels of integration and usage across the Australian community. This hard data is vital if ARDC is to help to deliver and gain optimal benefits from its considerable investment in ORCID to date.

Recommendations

As noted above, ORCID is becoming established as a de facto standard for person identification in the research space, and is becoming increasingly embedded within research administration, publication and reporting workflows. There are opportunities for ORCID to be incorporated into ARDC services, especially those which researchers might interact with, or those which interoperate with institutional systems. As the Australian consortium enters its fifth year, it is clear that the time to demonstrate tangible benefits from its investment in ORCID.

The first recommendation is that **ARDC as a key partner in the Australian ORCID consortium should work closely with AAF and consortium members to support benefits realisation activities**. There are a number of steps which could be taken to support the delivery of the consortium's goals:

- Evaluate ARDC services and integrations using the AAF-developed maturity model as a baseline exercise. This is a relatively simple first step, which will ensure that ARDC can articulate its position in the ORCID spectrum in terms comparable to the rest of the Australian community. Furthermore, it can provide a snapshot of ORCID integration which can be used to assess future progress. ARDC as a prime mover in the Australian consortium and as a nexus of PID expertise should be at the front of the pack.

⁸⁸ <https://knowledge-exchange.info/>

- Assess the data about ORCID usage and adoption that ARDC can gather or assemble. This is essential if we are to understand how iDs are really being used, and where the data flows are working best. These can then be used to quantify benefits, using, for example, similar tools to those developed by the Portuguese national funder.⁸⁹
- Maximise the breadth and depth of ORCID integrations in ARDC's own services. ARDC can lead by example and showcase methods to generate efficiencies, improve user experiences, and boost data provision and accuracy.
- Explore how ARDC could boost the maturity levels of partner integrations. Working alongside the support team at AAF, ARDC can focus on the platform level, ensuring that members are equipped to make the most of their ORCID membership.
- Consider introducing a requirement for ARDC-funded projects to either demonstrate an existing ORCID integration or to include an appropriate level of ORCID integration in their development plans.

Secondly, **ARDC as a service provider, information aggregator, and PID provider in its own right, should develop an ORCID benefits optimization strategy**, built upon its wider benefits realisation work. The difference between benefits realisation and optimization is an important distinction to draw, given ARDC's role as a nexus in the Australian research information network. To demonstrate the difference: In ORCID benefits realisation, the goal might be to ensure that each member has a set of functioning integrations that improve the efficiency or capability of their systems. In ORCID benefits optimization, ARDC would seek to enhance the linkages between those systems and national or international infrastructures, and to identify and facilitate the levels of data exchange between them, with an emphasis on data which have the highest strategic priority or practical value.

In practice, in this component, ARDC should:

- Explore how ARDC services can be leveraged to optimise the benefits of ORCID adoption in Australia. Opportunities include a Research Data Australia or RAiD auto-update mechanism.
- Support the generation of connections between more kinds of outputs and ORCID records. As outputs flow through ARDC-supported systems and other PID systems, they could be routed to the ORCID registry, helping researchers to re-use that information, improving attribution and credit for their creation, and helping to increase the ability of downstream users to trace the provenance and context of the work. This also has implications for research impact and integrity.
- Investigate the potential to act as a routing hub for research information coming into or from ORCID records. Italy and Portugal are models which spring to mind here. The Italian ORCID hub collected ORCID iDs and matched them to works in local repositories and the national publications database. In the process, it sought to fill gaps in both systems, and relayed information about collaborations or new publications that were missing from local systems. The Portuguese system, PT-CRIS, uses ORCID as a hub to

⁸⁹ As described here: António Luís Lopes, "Integrating a local CRIS with the PT-CRIS synchronisation ecosystem," *EuroCRIS* (2018): <http://hdl.handle.net/11366/650>

synchronise data between local and national systems, relaying updates in close to real time and eliminating the need for duplicative data entry.

Taken as a whole, these approaches should enable ARDC to provide quantitative evidence of the benefits of widespread ORCID adoption in Australia, to close gaps in coverage, and to maximise the strategic value of the data exchanges enabled by that optimal coverage.

Appendix 8: Australian Government Linked Data Working Group identifier recommendations.

Josh Brown, April 2020

Author's note: This is not a review of the AGLDWG service as a part of the ARDC portfolio. It is a review of the rationale⁹⁰ for bringing it on board as a potential complement to ARDC PID services. That rationale itself recommends a detailed review in the future, and I will not anticipate the inputs to or findings of that review.

Introduction

The Australian Government Linked Data Working Group (AGLDWG) was established in 2012 with a remit to improve data sharing across government departments and agencies using linked data technologies. It has developed a proto-PID system that uses Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) or web addresses for internet information resources. These resources are associated with and describe a range of real-world entities.

AGLDWG persistent URIs offer a very flexible method for identifying entities. URIs are commonplace, although the low technical resource needed to use them as PIDs in AGLDWG is at least partially offset by the manual processes involved in adding and reviewing registering resources⁹¹.

While AGLDWG is used across government and is in keeping with other international public sector approaches⁹², it is not necessarily an obvious match for ARDC's current PID portfolio. It is not a 'PID' in the sense that others in the ARDC portfolio are or aspire to be. The closest analogy is the PURL service. Some of the functionality of AGLDWG could be replicated by the Handle service, as noted in internal ARDC discussions of the service. It does not include the kind of registry or repository layer which has become associated with other PID services, such as DOIs, and as such has no central metadata component. Its status as a reference only may limit the service provision that can currently be built upon it.

However, the range of entities that are already identified using AGLDWG, such as street addresses⁹³ or commonwealth records⁹⁴ have obvious value to researchers across a range of disciplines as subjects of research in themselves and could be extremely useful in identifying the entities associated with a dataset or research infrastructure. As such, there is a case to be

⁹⁰ <https://docs.google.com/document/d/1us9sgWAJDT68yTvy4j0-m4tsYElmxbzAyqNfbob9xgk/edit>

⁹¹ The workflows involved in the registration and review processes are described in detail at <https://github.com/AGLDWG/guidelines/blob/master/PID-URI-Guidelines-v2.0.md>

⁹² See for example: <https://github.com/AGLDWG/guidelines/blob/master/PID-URI-Guidelines-v2.0.md#ref-CAB-2010>

⁹³ <http://linked.data.gov.au/dataset/gnaf/address/>

⁹⁴ <http://linked.data.gov.au/def/crs>

made for treating the existing service as a research resource, and for building new services on it which would enhance ARDC's other offerings.

Considerations

There is an inherent contradiction in the current recommendation set for AGLDWG within ARDC. It says no effort or cost would be incurred by maintaining the service as it is. There are a number of issues with this assertion.

To take on the service with no intention of committing resource to it would provide no improvement on the current situation where AGLDWG is described as having no resources to expand or maintain the current service, and consequently would bring no advantage to any of the parties involved.

Also, ARDC's internal discussions note that the service is unstable for unknown reasons. To take on an unstable service and to commit no resources at all to it would be simply to pick up reputational harm for no gain. Therefore, taking on AGLDWG will involve an unknown level of effort. Without knowing what the root of the problems are, it is hard to assess the viability, scalability, or persistability of the service. Taking on AGLDWG without making a commitment to diagnose and cure its current issues would serve no practical purpose at all, as noted, so accepting responsibility for providing AGLDWG requires ARDC to commit to doing what it takes to fix the service.

While delivering that fic would strengthen relationships between ARDC and the many public sector bodies currently invested in AGLDWG, and being seen to stabilise and strengthen the offering of AGLDWG could enhance ARDC's reputation, the associated risks are real. The unknown nature of AGLDWG's issues means it is not possible to accurately assess the resources needed. The fact that no other organisation stepped forward to pick it up may also indicate low interest. It would be wise to set a provisional end-point to ARDC's support for this initiative to contain potential costs. If no appetite is found in the research community for the service, that gives good grounds for ARDC to work with the government to secure a new host.

Strategically, the potential benefits of AGLDWG fall under the headings of two of the principles of this review. The first is that **partnership is leadership**. AGLDWG represents an opportunity to strengthen links with, and develop new services to support, federal and state governments. Secondly, **diversification beats wickedness**. By extending the range of approaches to persistent identification, ARDC can help to position itself to spot changes or trends and avoid becoming trapped in groupthink or a technological dead end.

Currently, AGLDWG is best seen as both research-adjacent and PID-adjacent. Exploring the ways that it could be brought into the core of ARDC's PID offering will help to shine light on the balance and rationale of the portfolio, and may offer a useful additional toolkit for researchers in identifying subjects of research.

Recommendations

The primary finding of this discussion is that **ARDC should follow the plan proposed in its internal deliberations**. It is too soon for a service review in the vein of the others presented here, as it is not a service. AGLDWG needs to be adopted and stabilised which in itself will deliver goodwill and reputational enhancements for ARDC. The core of the approach is exploration and evaluation, both of the soundness of the technical approach of AGLDWG to persistent identification, and of the levels of desire and readiness for such a service in the Australian research community.

ARDC should treat AGLDWG as an opportunity to experiment with more diverse approaches. In doing so, ARDC can bring together expertise from several teams (PIDs, vocabularies etc.) and see what innovations could be built upon the service. In evaluating adoption and appetite levels, questions such as “What business model could this service have?”, “What is its role in the research data space?”, and “Can it be spun out as an independent entity, or is a larger organisation (which may or may not turn out to be ARDC) the logical host?” should be central.

In any analysis preceding the ‘stabilisation’ of the service, **particular attention should be paid to commonalities in approach and functionality with other PID services, such as Handles.** If these systems could be used to underwrite the system, that would represent an opportunity to rationalise the number of technology stacks ARDC has to support. The disadvantage of that approach would be that it would lose some of the benefits of exploring new approaches to entity identification.

On balance, the fact that AGLDWG is ‘ARDC-adjacent’ represents a chance to strengthen its core offering, and the option to spin the service back out if that approach does not pan out. Boosting connections and bolstering the service as an aid to the federal and state governments are the benefits in either case, and both are worthwhile goals in themselves. AGLDWG is an opportunity that should be seized.